

Vivienne Sieber

Intercultural Competence through a Graphic Novel in Secondary ELT

An interdisciplinary approach with the graphic novel «When Stars Are Scattered»

Abstract

According to the UNHCR (the UN Refugee Agency), 108.4 million people were forcibly displaced in 2022, leading to our communities becoming more multicultural each year. This trend highlights the growing significance of having cognitive, affective, behavioral, and linguistic skills for engaging in effective and respectful conversations with individuals from other cultures. Additionally, today's world has become highly visual. It is, therefore, necessary to possess the ability to read and interpret graphics, a skill that can be learned at school. Interestingly, there is currently limited research exploring the development of intercultural competence in secondary schools, mainly through literature, graphic novels, or a cross-curricular approach incorporating geographical aspects. This project aims to present a new perspective, filling a previously neglected research gap concerning the use of authentic graphic memoirs and geographical expertise to develop intercultural competence in the ELT classroom. Data was collected qualitatively and quantitatively in a second-year class in a secondary school in the canton of Zurich. Activity booklets created

for a teaching unit using the graphic memoir *When Stars Are Scattered* (Mohamed and Jamieson 2020) were analyzed. The booklets, designed explicitly for the project, were qualitatively assessed. The students' self-reflection on their competencies and attitudes before and after reading were quantitatively examined. The qualitative analysis is based on the seven steps of Kuckartz and Rädiker's (2022) qualitative content analysis. The quantitative analysis, also based on Kuckartz and Rädiker (2022), used the quantitative analysis of qualitative data to compare the student's pre-reading evaluation to the post-reading evaluation.

The analysis showed that students improved their intercultural competence through working with the graphic memoir. The visual and cultural aspects of the memoir influenced and refined students' intercultural competence the most. These results argue for using graphic memoirs in ELT-classrooms and encourage a cross-curricular approach to teaching about migration.

Keywords

Intercultural Competence, English Language Teaching (ELT), teaching about migration, secondary school, graphic memoirs, Content and language integrated learning (CLIL)

Bibliografie

Sieber, Vivienne. 2024. *Intercultural Competence through a Graphic Novel in Secondary ELT*. Masterarbeit. Zürich: Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728858>

Dieses Werk steht unter der Lizenz CC-BY 4.0 International (Creative Commons: Namensnennung) – Copyright PH Zürich.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10728858

2024

Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich
Lagerstrasse 2
CH 8090 Zürich
www.phzh.ch

Intercultural Competence through a Graphic Novel in Secondary ELT

An interdisciplinary approach
with the graphic novel *"When Stars Are Scattered"*

Master's thesis at the Zurich University of Teacher Education
Department of Secondary School 1

Written by
Sieber, Vivienne

Handed in to
Prof. Dr. Nikola Mayer und Dr. Nicole Frey Büchel

Zurich, February 24

Abstract

According to the UNHCR (the UN Refugee Agency), 108.4 million people were forcibly displaced in 2022, leading to our communities becoming more multicultural each year. This trend highlights the growing significance of having cognitive, affective, behavioral, and linguistic skills for engaging in effective and respectful conversations with individuals from other cultures. Additionally, today's world has become highly visual. It is, therefore, necessary to possess the ability to read and interpret graphics, a skill that can be learned at school. Interestingly, there is currently limited research exploring the development of intercultural competence in secondary schools, mainly through literature, graphic novels, or a cross-curricular approach incorporating geographical aspects. This project aims to present a new perspective, filling a previously neglected research gap concerning the use of authentic graphic memoirs and geographical expertise to develop intercultural competence in the ELT classroom. Data was collected qualitatively and quantitatively in a second-year class in a secondary school in the canton of Zurich. Activity booklets created for a teaching unit using the graphic memoir *When Stars Are Scattered* (Mohamed and Jamieson 2020) were analyzed. The booklets, designed explicitly for the project, were qualitatively assessed. The students' self-reflection on their competencies and attitudes before and after reading were quantitatively examined. The qualitative analysis is based on the seven steps of Kuckartz and Rädiker's (2022) qualitative content analysis. The quantitative analysis, also based on Kuckartz and Rädiker (2022), used the quantitative analysis of qualitative data to compare the student's pre-reading evaluation to the post-reading evaluation.

The analysis showed that students improved their intercultural competence through working with the graphic memoir. The visual and cultural aspects of the memoir influenced and refined students' intercultural competence the most. These results argue for using graphic memoirs in ELT-classrooms and encourage a cross-curricular approach to teaching about migration.

Table of contents

List of figures and tables.....	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Research aims and objectives.....	9
3 Theory and current state of research	11
3.1 Intercultural competence	11
3.1.1 Definition and history.....	12
Byram's model	12
Critique of Byram's model	14
Deardorff's model.....	15
3.1.2 Intercultural competence in the Curriculum 21	16
3.1.3 Developing intercultural competence	18
3.1.4 Assessing intercultural competence	20
3.2 Literature in the ELT classroom	21
3.2.1 Literature in ELT to develop IC	23
3.2.2 Literature in ELT in the Curriculum 21.....	23
3.3 Graphic novels in the ELT classroom	24
3.3.1 Definition of graphic novels	24
3.3.2 Reading graphic narratives	26
3.3.3 Graphic narratives in the curriculum	27
3.3.4 Arguing for the use of graphic narratives in ELT.....	27
3.3.5 Graphic narratives for developing intercultural competence.....	28
3.3.6 Visual literacy through graphic narratives	29
3.4 Literature on refugee experiences.....	31
3.4.1 Literature on migration and refugee narratives	31
3.4.2 When Stars Are Scattered, a graphic memoir	31
3.5 Analysis of the graphic memoir When Stars Are Scattered.....	32
3.5.1 Age and gender appropriateness	33
3.5.2 Visual analysis	34

3.5.3 Analysis of the geographical aspects.....	36
3.5.4 Implementation in the project	37
3.6 Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL)	39
3.6.1 Definition of CLIL.....	39
3.6.2 Implementing CLIL.....	39
3.6.3 Discussion of the method.....	40
3.6.4 Using graphic narratives in CLIL	42
3.6.5 Implementation in the project	44
3.7 Cross-curricular teaching	45
3.7.1 History of cross-curricular teaching	45
3.7.2 Challenges of cross-curricular teaching.....	46
3.7.3 Implementing cross-curricular teaching	46
3.7.4 Cross-curricular teaching in Curriculum 21	47
3.7.5 Linking cross-curricular teaching to CLIL.....	47
4 Method.....	48
4.1 Participants	49
4.2 Data collection	50
4.3 Qualitative content analysis of qualitative data	52
4.4 Quantitative analysis of qualitative data	53
5 Results	54
5.1 Qualitative analysis results	54
5.1.1 Visual aspects of the graphic novel	54
5.1.2 Text-based aspects of the graphic novel	55
5.1.3 Geographical aspects of the graphic novel.....	56
5.1.4 Cultural aspects of the graphic novel.....	56
5.2 Quantitative analysis results	58
6 Discussion.....	59
6.1 Key findings and interpretation.....	59
6.2 Implications	62
6.3 Limitations	63

7 Conclusion.....	65
7.1 Reflection of the procedure.....	65
7.2 Consequences for teaching and outlook.....	66
8 Index of used aids and acknowledgments.....	67
9 Bibliography.....	68
10 Appendix.....	74
A) Lesson plan.....	74
B) Code book Excel.....	74
C) Answers from the students' activity booklets.....	74

List of figures and tables

Figure 1: Factors in intercultural communication by Byram (Byram 2008, 230)..	13
Figure 2: Pyramid model of intercultural competence by Deardorff (Deardorff and Hunter 2006).....	15
Figure 3: Process model of intercultural competence by Deardorff (Deardorff 2011, 67).....	16
Figure 4: Bar graph showing students' self-assessment regarding seven statements. The data shown was collected for this project.	58

1 Introduction

Images of crowded boats on the Mediterranean Sea, headlines of hundreds of refugees saved by the coastguard or drowned at sea, and never-ending political discussions of asylum and refugee policies fill our newspapers every day. At the end of 2022, 108.4 million people worldwide were, according to the UNHCR (The UN Refugee Agency), forcibly displaced “as a result of persecution, conflict, violence, human rights violations or events seriously disturbing public order” (UNHCR 2023). As a result of this, various countries in Europe, including Switzerland, receive refugees and offer them asylum. Because the topic is very present at the current time, a plethora of books, countless ones in English, about refugee experiences have come on the market in the past few years. Additionally, following the real-life effects and the importance of the topic, the Swiss secondary school curriculum includes migration in Africa as part of the geography curriculum (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017).

Based on the current state explained above, the following thesis uses a recent English publication on a refugee experience to focus on refugee migration in an English teaching classroom. The young adult graphic novel written and illustrated by Omar Mohamed and Victoria Jamieson, *When Stars Are Scattered*, is used to exemplify life in a refugee camp in Kenya, as experienced by the author Omar Mohamed (Mohamed and Jamieson 2020). He wrote the narrative to bring attention to the challenges faced by refugees, foster empathy, and enhance comprehension of the intricate issues related to displacement and refugee existence (Mohamed and Jamieson 2020). The combination of literature and geographical insights creates an ideal setting for students in secondary school to acquire knowledge about the refugee experience and gain empathy for the hardships refugees must endure. Understanding and sensitivity in these fields increases students’ intercultural competence (IC), which is critical in today’s global world.

Developing intercultural competence, including cultural awareness in the English-as-a-foreign-language (EFL) classroom, has been thoroughly researched by Byram (2021), Frank (2013), Nugent and Catalano (2015), and Cakir (2006).

Similarly, there has been a lot of research done on using literature in the classroom, mainly influenced by Carter and Burton, 1982, Maley and Moulding 1985, Brumfit and Carter, 1986, Collie and Slater, 1987, Carter, Walker, and Brumfit 1989, Carter and Long, 1991, and Bassnett and Grundy, 1993 (referenced in Khatib, Rezaei, and Derakhshan 2011, 201). Several studies have considered the positive effects of graphic novels in the EFL classroom (Lewis 2014; Kennedy and Chinokul 2022; Bland 2018; Schwarz 2006). Research has been conducted on incorporating refugee literature into the English language teaching (ELT) classroom by, for example, Zandian (2015), Shukla and Shukla (2006), and Prusse (2022). However, the interdisciplinary approach using the specific combination of English and geography perspectives in the ELT classroom has hardly been researched. Only one research article was found that used the *Adventures of Tintin* in an interdisciplinary approach with history, geography, and French (Llull 2014) to teach students historical and geographical knowledge and the French language. One study detailed how literature can help develop intercultural competence (Olagbaju 2020). No research was found about how a graphic novel about a refugee experience can be combined with a geographical perspective to develop students' intercultural competence.

The idea for the topic of this thesis comes from an interest in graphic novels. Because of this interest, I participated in a storytelling conference focusing on biographical and autobiographical narratives in the EFL classroom. Several stories on refugee experiences were presented at this conference. After reading *When Stars Are Scattered*, I realized I wanted to incorporate this book into my master's thesis for various reasons. The timeliness of the subject, captivating storytelling, Victoria Jamieson's unique drawing style, and the potential for an interdisciplinary teaching approach all contributed to my choice. Furthermore, in today's international world, possessing intercultural competencies is extremely important for understanding and empathizing with different cultures, fostering harmonious coexistence. As I aimed to explore a topic relevant to my future teaching career and considering the focus of interdisciplinary teaching during my studies at the Uni-

versity of Teaching Education Zurich, the topic of developing intercultural competence using an autobiographical graphic novel, combined with geographical aspects, resonated with me and appeared to be a suitable fit for my thesis.

Based on the previously described research focus of developing intercultural competence (IC) in the ELT classroom using the graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered* combined with geographical knowledge, the following research question was defined:

How do the visual, text-based, geographical, and cultural aspects of the graphic memoir *When Stars Are Scattered* in a CLIL (content and language integrated learning) setting influence the intercultural competence of students?

A teacher in the canton of Zurich taught a second secondary class of twenty students according to a lesson plan designed to develop intercultural competence with an activity booklet. The booklets and reflections were then qualitatively and quantitatively analyzed and linked to Byram's five *savoirs* to answer the research question. The research aims and objectives will be further detailed in Chapter 2.

To answer the research question thoroughly this thesis is structured as follows: Chapter 1 introduces the topic, and Chapter 2 gives an overview of the research aims and objectives. A theoretical basis is established in Chapter 3. Important terminology and concepts are explained, and the current state of research regarding intercultural competence, using literature and specifically graphic novels in the ELT classroom, the CLIL teaching method, and cross-curricular teaching is presented. The graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered* is also analyzed in this context. Chapter 4 presents the methodology used to gather and analyze the data. Chapter 5 gives a detailed overview of the results of the project. Chapter 6 discusses the obtained results and presents their limitations and implications. Lastly, Chapter 7 offers conclusions of this thesis. It reflects on the procedure and highlights the significance of this thesis for teaching and possible further research.

2 Research aims and objectives

The increasing frequency of intercultural situations, driven by the growing global movement of people due to fleeing and migration, necessitates that students are culturally competent. This demand is evident in the rising number of forcibly displaced people worldwide since 2000 (UNHCR 2023). These capabilities include the recognition of one's own and other cultures and using various skills to increase the understanding and appreciation of cultural differences and similarities (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 159, 167). It is, therefore, essential for students to have geographical and historical knowledge about a target culture, be able to analyze cultures and ways of life, including their own, understand identities and emotions, and develop empathy and curiosity towards a target culture (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 167). Following the importance of intercultural competence in today's global world, the skill is embedded in the English section of Curriculum 21, the curriculum used by the German-speaking cantons of Switzerland (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017).

There are numerous ways to develop students' intercultural competence in an English teaching classroom, including the use of critical incidents or authentic material (Nugent and Catalano 2015, 21-24) like texts and media (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 168-172) or literature (Olagbaju 2020, 42-43). Understanding a culture's background and historical context is also vital to understanding it fully. It is necessary to acknowledge the geographical aspects of a region and assess how they contribute to the culture in question. However, just one research article could be found on how students can be taught to become culturally competent using literature in the English teaching classroom (Olagbaju 2020), and no research was found that uses either literature in a cross-curricular approach with geography knowledge or graphic novels to teach intercultural competence. Graphic novels in the ELT classroom are necessary because our world is increasingly becoming more and more visual (Prusse 2022). Children and young adults are constantly confronted with images and text in real life or the digital world. This situation necessitates the skills to understand visuals and the ability to interpret them. Graphic novels offer a great opportunity to practice this competency in the

English classroom. This thesis aims to provide a new perspective and narrow the existing research gap by combining authentic graphic literature and geographical expertise to foster intercultural competence in the ELT classroom.

This project aims to develop secondary students' intercultural competence with a teaching plan that uses the graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered* (Jamieson and Mohamed 2020). It includes acquiring geographical knowledge about life in a refugee camp in Kenya. The students in a second-year secondary school (8th grade) class in the canton of Zurich worked with an activity booklet according to a lesson plan specifically created to include visual, text-based, geographical, and cultural aspects of the graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered* to develop and improve their intercultural competence. Their work and transformation were assessed after the defined teaching period.

3 Theory and current state of research

This chapter lays the theoretical foundation needed to create an instructional plan to achieve the project's goal mentioned in Chapters 1 and 2. It is based on the current state of research. Chapter 3.1 defines intercultural competence based on its use throughout history and puts the term into an educational context. Chapter 3.2 argues for the case of using literature in the English language teaching classroom. In Chapter 3.3, graphic novels are introduced, the term is defined, and an explanation of how to read them is given. Visual narratives are then put into an educational context and connected to intercultural competence. Chapter 3.4 discusses literature on refugee experiences, including the graphic novel used in this project, which will be analyzed in Chapter 3.5. Chapters 3.6 and 3.7 discuss and explain the methods of content and language-integrated learning (CLIL) and cross-curricular teaching, respectively.

3.1 Intercultural competence

This chapter argues for using the term intercultural competence (IC). It gives a definition and history of the term in Subchapter 3.1.1, including Byram's and Deardorff's models. IC is put into a Swiss educational context in Subchapter 3.1.2, and the development and assessment of the competence are discussed in Subchapters 3.1.3 and 3.1.4, respectively.

Terms like "cross-cultural competence, international competence, global citizenship, intercultural effectiveness, cultural intelligence, cultural competence, transcultural competence, and intercultural sensitivity" (Deardorff 2020, 493) are often used interchangeably to "describe the concept of intercultural competence" (Deardorff 2020, 493). According to Deardorff's research (2020, 493), specific academic disciplines use certain terms more. The most widely used terms in education are 'global competence' and 'intercultural competence.' The two terms can be used synonymously with just slight differences in emphasis. Because Deardorff (2020) does not explain this difference, ChatGPT was asked: "difference between global and intercultural competence in a table" (ChatGPT, 20. November 2023). According to ChatGPT, the main difference is that global competence focuses on

understanding and engaging with global issues. In contrast, intercultural competence emphasizes navigating cultural differences and fostering effective communication across cultures (ChatGPT, 20. November 2023). In this thesis, only the term intercultural competence will be used to avoid confusion since it focuses on communication between cultures and can, therefore, be focused on in an ELT classroom.

3.1.1 Definition and history

To this day, the concept of intercultural competence is difficult to define (Deardorff 2020, 493). Deardorff's study from 2006 attempted to find a consensus on a definition of intercultural competence according to educators and international intercultural experts. The agreed-upon definition was "the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately in intercultural situations based on one's intercultural knowledge, skills and attitudes" (Deardorff 2006, 248). This definition is mainly based on the 1997 model of intercultural competence by Michael Byram.

Byram's model

The idea of intercultural competence was coined by the researcher Michael Byram in the nineties. He defines intercultural competence as one part of intercultural communicative competence (the other being linguistic competence). Both competencies are imperative when teaching a foreign language (Byram 2021, 28; Byram 1997, 22). The model he created, showing the factors needed for successful intercultural communication, is mainly based on the work done by European researcher van Ek in 1986 (Byram 1997, 9). Van Ek and other previous researchers, such as Canale and Swain, 1980, Halliday, 1975, and Hymes, 1972 failed, however, to include "the ability to use language appropriately according to context and purpose" (Hoff 2020, 56) as well as "ignor[ed] the significance of the social identities and cultural competence of the learner" (Byram 1997, referenced in Hoff 2020, 56) in their research. Byram's model included these missing aspects. He created a conceptual model with the "qualities of a competent *intercultural speaker*" (Hoff 2020,

56). The illustration (figure 1) consists of five aspects, namely 'savoirs, savoir comprendre, savoir s'engager, savoir apprendre/faire and savoir être' (Byram 2008, 230). Byram, Nichols, and Stevens (2001), Byram (2008), Byram (2021), Hoff (2020), and other re-

Intercultural Competence⁸¹

Figure 1: Factors in intercultural communication by Byram (Byram 2008, 230)

searchers have explained the factors in detail. The following explanations are based on the just mentioned sources.

The English term for *savoirs* is knowledge. To be an intercultural competent language learner, one must know how social groups function and how identities work (Byram, Nichols, and Stevens 2001, 6; Byram 2008, 231; Byram 2021, 134; Hoff 2020, 56). One should know about "products and practices in one's own and in one's interlocutor's country" (Byram 2021, 134). This knowledge should also include how society has changed over the years and how society views itself and is viewed by others. Important to note here is that the "knowledge [should be] about how other people see oneself as well as some knowledge about other people" (Byram, Nichols, and Stevens 2001, 6).

The terms *savoir comprendre* and *savoir apprendre/faire* both define skills an intercultural competent learner should possess. *Savoir comprendre* covers the "skills of interpreting and relating" (Byram 2008, 232) to other cultures. Mastering this skill includes interpreting and explaining "a document or event from another culture" (Byram 2008, 232) and connecting it to one's own culture. The skills of *savoir apprendre/faire* are about "discovery and interaction" (Byram 2008, 232). They explain the "ability to acquire new knowledge of a culture and cultural practices" (Byram 2008, 232) and then use this information in social interactions (Byram, Nichols, and Stevens 2001, 6; Byram 2008, 232; Byram 2021, 137; Hoff

2020, 56).

Savoir être can be understood as the learner's attitude toward cultures. It includes the curiosity and openness to let go of beliefs and disbeliefs about one's own and foreign cultures. Furthermore, it incorporates the ability to 'decenter,' which means to analyze one's values and behaviors from an outsider's perspective (Byram, Nichols, and Stevens 2001, 5; Byram 2008, 230; Byram 2021, 131; Hoff 2020, 56).

The last aspect needed to be culturally competent, according to Byram's model of 1997, is *savoir s'engager*. This *savoir* can be translated as having critical cultural awareness. It includes being aware of one's own and one's culture's values and the ability to evaluate and critically evaluate these values. It also encompasses the ability to "interact and mediate in intercultural exchanges in accordance with explicit criteria, negotiating where necessary a degree of acceptance of them by drawing upon one's knowledge, skills and attitudes" (Byram 2008, 233). This explanation, therefore, means that the last skill includes all the previous factors and combines them to make the learner a competent intercultural communicator (Byram, Nichols, and Stevens 2001, 7; Byram 2008, 233; Byram 2021, 140; Hoff 2020, 56).

Critique of Byram's model

Concerns and critiques about Byram's model have been raised by various researchers in the 21st century (Hoff 2020, 57). Hoff (2020, 57) summarizes the relevant issues as follows:

- "Problems with the concepts of culture and identity.
- Conflictual dimensions of intercultural encounters must be captured in a more nuanced manner.
- More varied communication contexts must be taken into account.
- The need to "de-center" interculturality.
- Problems with assessing ICC [intercultural communicative competence]."

The concepts of culture and identity can be problematic in Byram's model because they are linked to countries and nations. In the second edition of Byram's book about teaching and assessing intercultural communicative competence

(Byram 2021), he realizes that the notion of culture can also apply to other groups, like ethnic minorities (Byram 2021, 42). The aspect of assessing ICC, specifically intercultural competence, will be discussed in Subchapter 3.1.4.

Deardorff's model

Darla Deardorff proposed an alternative and more detailed version of Byram's model of intercultural competence in 2004 (Deardorff and Hunter 2006). Her pyramid model (*figure 2*) contains more specific elements based on her study of the definition of intercultural competence (Deardorff and Hunter 2006, 72). Because a pyramid model has limitations, she updated her model and created a process model of intercultural competence (*figure 3*) (Deardorff and Hunter 2006, 73).

Pyramid Model of Intercultural Competence

Figure 2: Pyramid model of intercultural competence by Deardorff (Deardorff and Hunter 2006)

As is visible by looking at the two models (figures 2 and 3), they comprise the same elements but are arranged differently. Both models start with attitudes, which is vital because the attitudes of respect, openness and curiosity are the basis for acquiring new knowledge and skills (Deardorff and Hunter 2006, 73-74). Both models also include internal outcomes from intercultural competence and external outcomes that can be assessed. These outcomes are a first in intercultural competence models (Deardorff and Hunter 2006, 74).

Figure 3: Process model of intercultural competence by Deardorff (Deardorff 2011, 67)

Compared to the pyramid model, the process model shows the movement between the different elements and that it is possible to go from one thing to another without passing the ones in between (Deardorff and Hunter 2006, 73). The cycle form also shows the “ongoing process” and the “complexity of intercultural competence development” (Deardorff and Hunter 2006, 73). It is a lifelong process and does not end with one cycle (Deardorff and Hunter 2006, 73).

3.1.2 Intercultural competence in the Curriculum 21

The canton of Zurich’s curriculum was implemented in 2017 and includes the foreign languages English, French, and Italian. All these languages are divided into six subcategories, namely listening, reading, speaking, writing, focus on language, and focus on cultures (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 1-3). According to the introduction to languages in the curriculum, the “ability to use language consciously and responsibly in communication” is one of the main goals of education (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 5). The introductory text

explains that language is key in showing respect, tolerance, and understanding and is the basis for living together peacefully. As Byram highlighted in 1997, the curriculum acknowledges that language competency must include linguistic and intercultural competencies (Byram 1997, 22; Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 5).

The category 'focus on cultures' can be linked to intercultural competence as defined in the chapter above. There are several parallels to the aspects included in Byram's model of intercultural competence. The curriculum category 'focus on cultures' is divided into three parts.

The first part focuses on *Kenntnisse* or knowledge. Students should know aspects of English-speaking cultures and understand cultural similarities and differences to their own. This aspect is very similar to Byram's aspect of *savoirs* or knowledge (Byram 2008, 230). It includes knowledge of social groups and practices without interpreting or judging (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 74).

The second part puts the student's *Haltungen* or attitudes at the center. Again, to link to Byram's model (Byram 2008, 230), this is the same as *savoir être*. It focuses on the students' attitudes towards the English-speaking world and teaches them to reflect on cultural diversity (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 75).

The third aspect of the curriculum is *Handlungen* or actions. This aspect of the curriculum entails Byram's *savoir s'engager*. Namely, it includes encountering English-speaking people and realizing that norms and values are relative and different for people from different cultures. It also allows students to use their cultural knowledge in interactions (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 76).

Looking at the curriculum critically, one notices that it primarily focuses on students interacting with English-speaking communities rather than using the English language as a *lingua franca*. This concern is mentioned by Hoff (2020, 57) as a

relevant issue of Byram's model of intercultural competence. Hoff (2020, 62) explains that at the beginning of the use of the term, "the intercultural speaker" mostly needed "the ability to communicate effectively with native speakers of a given target language" (Baker 2011, referenced in Hoff 2020, 62). This is what it seems like the curriculum wants students to achieve (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 74-76). It is, however, essential to consider the growing number of interactions where English is used as a "*lingua franca* between individuals" (Hoff 2020, 62) of non-English speaking backgrounds. It is therefore not just important to know the culture of the 'native speaker' of the past but rather be competent to interact with many different cultures and backgrounds (Hoff 2020, 62-63).

3.1.3 Developing intercultural competence

Byram (2021, 82) suggests that intercultural competence elements can be expressed as objectives. For example, an objective for knowledge is: "knowledge about/of the processes of social interaction in one's interlocutor's country" (Byram 2008, 231). These objectives make complex elements like attitudes visible to an outside observer through, for example, actual performances like role play (Byram 2021, 84). Nevertheless, the objectives described by Byram (2008, 230-233; 2021, 84-90) are complex, and some might not even be achievable in the classroom (Byram 2021, 91). Furthermore, it is essential to note that some of the objectives might already be present in the students before the teacher aims to develop them (Byram 2021, 62). This subchapter will be organized according to Byram's five *savoirs* to structure the development of intercultural competence.

Positive attitudes must be cultivated to develop intercultural competence in the ELT classroom (Deardorff and Hunter 2006, 73-74). Positive attitudes entail students being open to learning about and willing to reconsider their viewpoints on different cultures. To achieve this, the teacher must first break down cultural barriers and stereotypical thinking (Cakir 2006, 158). This can be done by emphasizing similarities between people and then discussing differences between members of students' families, schools, and cultures (Cakir 2006, 158).

Bon (2022, 891) mentions the methods of comparison, cultural assimilation,

and cultural island to promote intercultural competencies. These ideas develop the skills (*savoir comprendre* and *savoir apprendre/faire*) in Byram's model (Byram 1997). The comparison method consists "of a comparison between the learner's culture and foreign cultures (Bon 2022, 891). This comparison can be made by watching videos or reading documents about, for example, daily life in a foreign country and the home country. Social media is also great for observing other cultures (Bon 2022, 891-892). In the process of cultural assimilation, students are given several possible reactions to a situation and are required to choose the one they deem correct. Subsequently, teachers then clarify to the students that the validity of each option is dependent on the culture one is in (Bon 2022, 892).

Bon (2022) additionally highlights the potential of teaching students in diverse cultural knowledge (*savoirs*) and enhancing their cultural awareness (*savoir s'engager*) (Bon 2022, 891). The first can be acquired through, for example, web quests, in which students find as much information about a specific group as possible (Frank, 2013, 7). Another possibility is to use literature and find information about a particular culture's products, practices, and ways of life (Burwitz-Melzer 2001, 29).

In strengthening cultural awareness (*savoir s'engager*), Nugent and Catalano (2015, 17) highlight the necessity of providing students with tasks and the necessary scaffolds that allow them to practice the skill of critical evaluation. The first step includes identifying and reflecting on the students' "preconceived ideas, judgments, and stereotypes toward individuals from the target culture" (Nugent and Catalano 2015, 17). The origin of these ideas and beliefs can then be analyzed and evaluated if they are reasonable (Nugent and Catalano 2015, 18). The next step should consist of activities that focus on the students considering new values and beliefs through the research they carried out before. Students must do these discovery tasks alone or in groups so the teacher does not force their views on the students (Nugent and Catalano 2015, 18). In the final step, students should use their newly gained insights and knowledge in real-life or simulated encounters (Nugent and Catalano 2015, 19). The last phase proposed by Nugent and Catalano (2015, 18) is the same as Bon (2022), Cakir (2006), and Banjongjit and

Boonmoh (referenced in Bon 2022)'s idea of role play.

Role-play can include situations in a foreign country where students must act accordingly (Bon 2022, 891). Role-plays, "reading, films, simulations, [and] games can" (Cakir 2006, 157) "promote cultural understanding" and "cross-cultural dialogues" (Cakir 2006, 157) in the EFL classroom. Role-plays are the closest classrooms can get to real life and come close to individual learning experiences, which Byram (2021, 62) mentions as the third place to acquire intercultural competence. According to Banjongjit and Boonmoh (referenced in Bon 2022, 892), role-play is "the most successful way to develop students' IC".

Finally, Frank (2013, 10) brings up the idea of a culture journal as an over-reaching method of developing IC and making the components visible. The journal, where students write down their feelings and experiences "as they become more aware of their own culture and the one being studied" (Frank 2013, 10), can allow students to reflect on what they have learned and serve as a basis for class discussions. The basis for their reflection could be in class activities or their own experiences outside of the classroom (Frank 2013, 10).

3.1.4 Assessing intercultural competence

Considering the clear objectives by Byram (2008, 230-233), assessing intercultural competence should be relatively easy. However, there are different views on this. According to Deardorff's study of intercultural competence (2006, 248), there is a consensus on the need to assess students' IC. However, Byram (2008, 219-220) points out uncertainties in evaluating IC. One specific concern Byram raises involves the assessment of one's willingness to be open to or curious about different things (Byram 2008, 221). He emphasizes that these qualities may be perceived "as ideological, reflecting a particular set of values that is not necessarily shared by all social groups" (Byram 2021, 221). For instance, being open to diverse cultures and beliefs may not be socially acceptable in certain cultures. Byram suggests that implementing an assessment system that labels openness as 'good' in education or careers could be considered hegemonic because such a system would enforce a particular set of values on individuals, potentially disregarding or

marginalizing other cultural perspectives.

Byram does see, however, that the current state of schools requires some assessment. He, therefore, suggests less traditional ways of evaluating IC and proposes portfolios or profiles (Byram 2008, 224). Deardorff (2011, 74) also recommends the notion of portfolios. She suggests splitting the complex objectives (Byram 2021, 84) into “manageable portions” (Deardorff 2011, 74) and assessing their outcomes using one direct and one indirect measure (Deardorff 2011, 74-75). Direct evidence includes learning contracts, e-portfolios, critical reflections, or performances in intercultural situations. Indirect evidence is usually collected through interviews or surveys (Deardorff 2011, 74-76).

3.2 Literature in the ELT classroom

This chapter argues for the use of literature in the ELT classroom, gives insight into using it to develop IC in Subchapter 3.2.1, and puts it in the context of Curriculum 21 in Subchapter 3.2.2.

Using literature in classrooms is not new, but whether it is necessary is still debatable. Many people view reading as time-consuming (Kennedy and Chinokul 2020, 158), are not intrinsically motivated to read, or have a low reading comprehension level, which hinders them from understanding authentic material (Gultom, Frans, and Cellay 2022, 47).

These concerns are misplaced, however, as several authors (Prusse 2022, 56; Daskalovska and Dimova 2012, 1182; Gultom, Frans, and Cellay 2022, 46) have proven. Teaching literature is important because it provides students with authentic material (Daskalovska and Dimova 2012, 1182) and allows them to develop skills needed in the real world by bringing the world into the classroom (Prusse 2022, 56). Gultom, Frans, and Cellay (2022, 46) add that literature as a teaching method allows students to overcome barriers concerning vocabulary, pronunciation, grammatical awareness, and expressing thoughts.

Thaler (2016, 23) presents six arguments for using literary texts in EFL class-

rooms: language development, social prestige, interpretational openness, motivational value, personal enrichment, and intercultural learning. Language development can occur by working with the text in the four basic skills (reading, speaking, writing, listening) or with its linguistic aspects. Reading in class is linked to social prestige because literature holds a high social status. Similarly, reading a literary text is often a welcome change to grammar teaching and regular classroom routine, which motivates students and interests them. Seeing that no two people will understand a text in the same way, there will be numerous interpretations of texts in a class. These different evaluations allow for discussions and individual responses to text interpretation. Using a text from a foreign country will enable students to become acquainted with new cultures and ways of life. If used correctly, it may lead to students being more open and tolerant towards other cultures. Students can enrich their development through this and by identifying with a text's character (Thaler 2016, 24). Chiappini (2021, 24) adds to Thaler's list of reasons for using literature in the classroom by reinforcing the argument of developing and using key competencies and adding aspects of critical and creative thinking and emotional and cultural awareness.

Finally, it is especially crucial to implement the reading of literary texts in the ELT classroom because of the recent Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) findings. It shows that "every fourth child leaves primary school in Germany without sufficient reading skills" (Anderson 2023). The PIRLS study of 2021 (IEA PIRLS 2023) tested the reading skills of about 400,000 students in 57 countries. Because the survey is carried out every five years, statements can be made about trends. However, the COVID-19 pandemic and associated school closures may have impacted the 2021 testing. Consequently, trends from 2016 to 2021 should be interpreted with this consideration.

Of the 32 countries that participated in the study in the past several years, thus enabling a trend analysis, 65% had lower average reading rates in 2021 than in 2016. Of these 65%, 38% had improved in 2016 compared to the testing in 2011, and 14% had shown no change. These results suggest that the pandemic

harmed fourth-grade reading achievement. Following the study's results and possible negative trends, reading in an ELT classroom should continually be a standard practice.

3.2.1 Literature in ELT to develop IC

As previously mentioned by Thaler (2016, 23), literature in the ELT classroom can be used for intercultural learning. Using literature for this purpose has also been researched by the authors Burwitz-Melzer (2001), Hoffmann and Mastellotto (2023), Kramsch (1993 referenced in Thaler 2016, 70), Bredella (2002 referenced in Thaler 2016, 70), Delanoy (2002 referenced in Thaler 2016, 70), and Müller-Hartmann and Schocker-von-Dithfurt (2004 referenced in Thaler 2016, 70). Because everyone learns the cultural ways of life, values, and background knowledge of the society they live in implicitly from an early age, they are inherently reflected in later written narratives (Hoffmann and Mastellotto 2023, 23). Thaler (2016, 70) explains that in reading texts written by foreign authors representing that linguistic and cultural group, students can experience these values and ways of life and are forced to compare them to their own. This comparison can lead to curiosity about the other culture, students decentering, changing perspectives, and reflecting on their own culture, thus developing intercultural awareness (Thaler 2016, 70). Hoffmann and Mastellotto (2023, 24) clarify that learning does not happen automatically but rather arises through educators' prompts for reflection and discussion and the learner's interaction with the text.

3.2.2 Literature in ELT in the Curriculum 21

The English curriculum used in the canton of Zurich works on the six essential skills: listening, reading, speaking, writing, 'focus on language,' and 'focus on culture' (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 13-14). Compared to the German curriculum, where there is a specific subskill called 'focus on literature,' there is no equivalent in the English curriculum (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017, 14). It is, however, possible to integrate literature in any of the six English skills. Depending on the work done with the literary text, the focus will be different. Therefore, the curriculum allows the development of students' intercultural competencies using a literary text.

3.3 Graphic novels in the ELT classroom

In Subchapter 3.3.1, graphic novels are defined according to several authors, and the most critical aspects of the medium will be explained in Subchapter 3.3.2. Subchapters 3.3.3 and 3.3.4 then argue for using graphic narratives in foreign language teaching, and Subchapters 3.3.5 and 3.3.6 explain how intercultural and visual competence can be achieved using graphic novels, respectively.

3.3.1 Definition of graphic novels

Blending verbal and pictorial text has been done for years, but Will Eisner and Scott McCloud did the most groundbreaking studies reflecting on this field of literature. Eisner coined the term 'graphic novel' in 1978 with the publication *A Contract with God* and then theorized on this in his *Comics and Sequential Art* in 1985 (Eisner 1985). McCloud defined comics and gave an extensive background in his *Understanding Comics* in 1993 (McCloud 1993). To this day, these two different frameworks for theorizing pictorial art lay the groundwork for contemporary engagement with the topic.

The critical difference between the two theories is that Eisner proposed the umbrella term 'sequential art' to describe "a means of creative expression and literary form that deals with the arrangement of pictures or images and words to narrate a story or dramatize an idea" (Eisner 1985, 5). Through the title *Comics and Sequential Art*, he clearly distinguishes between sequential art and comics. According to Eisner's understanding, all formats, including images or images and words, such as picture books, airline safety instruction sheets, or photo strips, can be seen as forms of sequential art (Eisner 1985, 5-7).

Conversely, McCloud uses Eisner's term 'sequential art' but makes it more specific. He turns it around, saying, "all sequential art is comics" (Oziewicz 2018, 27; McCloud 1993, 9) instead of "all comics [are] [...] examples of sequential art [...]" (Oziewicz 2018, 27). McCloud thus says that comics are arranged visual elements, including pictures and other imagery, in a deliberate order to convey information and elicit an aesthetic reaction from the observer. Therefore, any story told in images can be seen as comics (Oziewicz 2018, 27; McCloud 1993, 5 - 9).

Although McCloud found his definition to resonate highly, some critical voices have been raised. Nodelman (2012, 463) specifically pointed out his disagreement with the fact that, according to McCloud, picture books are comics. He says these two formats are very different (Nodelman 2012, 463). Oziewicz (2018, 27) discussed this phenomenon with his class and concluded that over half of his students did not agree that picture books are a type of comic book. Another concern Oziewicz raises is that 'comic' "is a culturally loaded term" (Oziewicz 2018, 28), whereas 'sequential art' is fuzzier. Consequently, it is often found more suitable to use 'sequential art' or terms like 'graphic narratives' or 'visual narratives' as the umbrella term rather than comics to define art forms blending images and text (Oziewicz 2018, 28).

Based on the above definition, graphic novels can be under the umbrella term 'sequential art.' Since there are countless forms of sequential art (Eisner 1985), the question arises of how graphic novels can be differentiated from other terms under the umbrella expression. In Eisner's conceptualization of sequential art, graphic novels constitute one of the four primary formats within this domain. The remaining three formats are comics, picture books, and comic strips. It's important to note that this format is distinct from the genre and is not restricted by content or narrative type; instead, it serves as the vehicle for conveying the storyline (Oziewicz 2018, 29).

Unlike the other three formats, graphic novels represent self-contained works of fiction and nonfiction published in book form. Like the different formats, they rely on integrating visual and textual elements through sequential art. However, graphic novels provide greater creative freedom regarding the design, style, and interplay between images and text than the other three formats. Moreover, graphic novels offer versatility in the amount of text they can encompass, a flexibility not shared by comic strips, comics, or picture books. There is no upper limit to the text volume a graphic novel can incorporate. Additionally, categorizing "graphic novels as a format" (Oziewicz 2018, 30) rather than a genre makes it evident that they can encompass various genres, including memoirs, biographies, romance, fantasy, and historical fiction (Oziewicz 2018, 30).

Based on his work, *A Contract with God*, Eisner established criteria for graphic novels. Translated from Eder's (2016, 157) German list, they are the following:

- "Comics in a book format
- Graphic literature that addresses an adult audience
- Literary demands as well as self-reflective, auto-fictional narrative attitude
- Non-serialized, fictional, or non-fictional narrative
- Experimental use of text-image connections
- Breaking down the page design and panel arrangement typical of the magazine comic
- Distribution via bookstores."

3.3.2 Reading graphic narratives

Reading visual narratives consists of more than just following words from top to bottom like one would when consuming a regular text-based novel. Several terms, which will be explained in this subchapter, are needed to successfully discuss and read graphic novels.

Panels. Panels can be seen as the pearls on a string that make up part of a pearl necklace. Strung together, they produce a complete story for a set time (Grünewald 2022, 32). A panel usually depicts one action through image and text (Lewis 2017, 167). Panels can be of different sizes and shapes and read from left to right, top to bottom, or a mixture of both (Grünewald 2022, 19 - 20; Lewis 2017, 167). Generally, the bigger a panel, the more detailed an image is drawn and the more important it is (Lewis 2017, 167).

Balloons. Thoughts and sentences produced by the characters in a graphic novel are shown in balloons. They contain informal and direct speech. The lines used to draw the balloons indicate the type of utterance represented. Ordinary speech is signaled with a balloon with a solid line, shouting has a jagged line, and whispering is depicted with dotted lines (Lewis 2017, 167).

Captions. Sometimes, the text is not written into the balloons but is displayed in a rectangle within a panel instead. These are narrations of the story and provide background information (Lewis 2017, 167).

Sound words. In comparison to regular novels, graphic novels often use onomatopoeic words. These are words like *splash* or *ow* that sound like the action they are describing.

Motion lines. These lines convey movement, heat, or smell.

Gutters. The spaces between the panels are called gutters. They are often white and never include images, but they are essential to the story. Gutters include actions left to the reader's imagination (Lewis 2017, 167). An example would be a car in a parking lot in the first panel and an empty parking lot in the second. Left to the reader's imagination in the gutter between the panels is that the car drove away.

Knowing and understanding the parts of a graphic novel are vital as they allow for a deeper interpretation of the depicted images. They can be analyzed regarding the characters, movement, communication, location, size, order of panels (Grünewald 2022, 19-32), and colors (Fresacher 2017, 71).

3.3.3 Graphic narratives in the curriculum

In Curriculum 21, under the skill of reading, there is a competence that requires students to be able to dive into stories illustrated with images. The examples given are comics and graphic narratives (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017). Using graphic novels in the EFL classroom is imperative to acquire this competence.

3.3.4 Arguing for the use of graphic narratives in ELT

As specified by Rouse (2021), who wrote the article *Graphic Novels Continue to Push Boundaries* in the *Library Journal*, the market share of graphic novels increased by 6% between 2019 and 2020, and the tendency continued in 2021. Graphic novels have recently become increasingly popular (Lewis 2017, 166). They have gained acceptance and approval from young adult readers and in educational contexts (Lewis 2017, 166).

Gultom, Frans, and Cellay (2022) mention a study that showed that graphic

novels significantly improved students' reading comprehension levels and allowed them to develop intrinsic motivation for reading. Their study conducted at a university in Indonesia with 118 first-year English literature students confirmed the previous study's results. They also found that graphic novels motivate students to improve their speaking level and quantity (Gultom, Frans, and Cellay 2022, 47-52). Bakar, Ahmad, and Yunus (2020, 44) add the heightened motivation to learn about literature in their paper. Although Gultom, Frans, and Cellay's study focused on improving speaking fluency for EFL learners, their positive results on using GNs to help teach students about grammar, social issues, and culture (Gultom, Frans, and Cellay 2022, 52) can also be transferred to writing. The two studies also proved that working with graphic novels helps students to deduce meaning (Gultom, Frans, and Cellay 2022, 52; Bakar, Ahmad, and Yunus 2020, 44). The Malaysian researchers Bakar, Ahmad, and Yunus (2020, 44) add the argument that graphic novels may also improve memory and create a strong engagement between students and the text.

Additionally, the very recent study by Mayer (2022) highlights the use of simplified literature in EFL classrooms to achieve experiences of success in secondary school students. Simplified literature is defined as literature with some complexity reduction, such as with the layout or language, and additional assistance, such as illustrations or visuals (Mayer 2022, 90).

The arguments presented above clearly show that graphic novels positively impact the ELT classroom and should thus represent an inherent part of teaching English as a foreign language.

3.3.5 Graphic narratives for developing intercultural competence

Apart from using graphic narrations to develop students' reading skills, visual narrations can also be used to foster cultural learning (Llull 2014). Habegger-Conti (2021, 53) supports this assertion in her introduction, which summarizes different research. Picture books and graphic narratives can be used to explore con-

flict, learn about complex power structures, and develop cultural literacy and intercultural competencies by helping students see some differences and similarities between their world and the one represented in the story. This chapter will explain how intercultural competences can be developed by using graphic novels.

A specific type of graphic narrative that is especially useful in intercultural education is accounts of or about refugees (Habegger-Conti 2021, 53). Specifically, Habegger-Conti (2021, 53) mentions those for young adult readers, like *When Stars Are Scattered* (2020) or *Illegal* (2018). These types of narratives enable an ethical encounter.

The term ethical encounters, coined by the philosopher Judith Butler (referenced in Habegger-Conti 2021, 54), questions what conditions lead to a feeling of moral responsibility for people far away. Butler surmises that to see ourselves as part of all the people living on the planet, we must “embrace an ethics of cohabitation that depends upon the ‘reversibility of proximity and distance’” (Habegger-Conti 2021, 54). For an ethical encounter to occur, accepting and acknowledging this cohabitation and interconnectedness is necessary. Connecting this with intercultural education, students must see people “who live in faraway places as part of a ‘we’ rather than a ‘them’” (Habegger-Conti 2021, 54).

The ‘we’ type of thinking proposed by Habegger-Conti (2021) can be established by highlighting similarities between the cultures and specific individuals that can be seen as part of a different culture (Wang and Donovan 2020). Furthermore, using suitable works of literature can irritate students, leading to reflection on previously assumed natural ways of thinking or viewpoints (Freitag-Hild 2022, 113).

3.3.6 Visual literacy through graphic narratives

According to several authors (Eisenmann 2022, 58-60; Prusse 2022, 56; Gillenwater 2009, 33; Burmark 2008, 6), students in today’s world do not just need to be able to read, analyze, and interpret regular text-based literature, but also need to be able to understand all types of multiple digital media formats such as visual and auditive media, all kinds of hybrid and digital media as well as media

arrangements. This competency is essential today because one of the primary forms of communication has shifted from a merely text-based one to a visual one, and images can challenge the understanding and interpretation of the world (Eisenmann 2022, 58-60; Frey and Fisher 2008, 5). Students in secondary education are part of this visually shaped world and are constantly confronted by images they need to interpret and evaluate (Eisenmann 2022, 58-60). This skill must be taught and practiced at school because it helps students “acquire knowledge, develop empathy, and cultivate critical literacy” (Prusse 2022, 56). Eisenmann defines being visually competent as being able to “interpret, evaluate, use, and create visual media” (2022, 60). Burmark’s definition of visual literacy backs up Eisenman’s definition: “To be visually literate, they [the students] must learn to ‘read’ (consume/interpret) images and ‘write’ (produce/use) visually rich communications” (2008, 5). “Visually competent people are critical consumers of visual media” (Eisenmann 2022, 60), which is unavoidable today. Graphic narrations, and graphic novels specifically, are the ideal medium to teach both print (text-based media) literacy and visual (visual media) literacy (Gillenwater 2009, 33).

Eisenmann (2022, 57) and Gillenwater (2009, 33, 35) both see graphic narrations and graphic novels as suitable mediums for teaching visual literacy and should be incorporated into all school subjects. They use a combination of literary and pictorial depictions (Eisenmann 2022, 67), one of the most complex interactions between these two modes of communication (Prusse 2022, 56; Gillenwater 2009, 35). To understand sequential stories, including graphic novels, one needs to understand both the text-based and the image-based information, as they complement each other, and the story can only be fully understood if the two are synthesized (Gillenwater 2009, 35). One also needs to be competent in several reading and writing practices. Some of these include understanding sequential pictures, interpreting characters’ gestures, and understanding the plot of a story (Eisenmann 2022, 64). These skills can be summarized under the term visual literacy (Eisenmann 2022, 59).

3.4 Literature on refugee experiences

Subchapter 3.4.1 gives an overview of significant literature on migration and refugee narratives. The term graphic memoir is then defined, and its example, *When Stars Are Scattered* (Mohamed and Jamieson 2020), is put into the context of literature on refugee experiences in Subchapter 3.4.2.

3.4.1 Literature on migration and refugee narratives

Multicultural societies are not a rarity in today's world, and the melting pot of cultures is intensifying, as seen in the 2022 statistics released by the European Commission (European Commission 2022). It is, therefore, not surprising that publications on migration and refugee experiences are diverse and plentiful.

Traditional books and graphic narrations for young adult readers about migration and refugees can include *Boy Overboard* by Morris Gleitzman, *Refugee* by Alan Gratz, *Refugee Boy* by Benjamin Zephaniah, *Illegal* by Eoin Colfer, Andrew Donkin, and Giovanni Rigano, or *When Stars Are Scattered* by Omar Mohamed and Victoria Jamieson (Prusse 2022, 57). The texts tell stories of refugee children and young adults. Compared to *When Stars Are Scattered* and *Refugee Boy*, which were both written by non-white males and focus on the reality of life, which can be tedious at times, *Boy Overboard*, *Illegal*, and *Refugee* concentrate mainly on the troublesome and adventurous journey of fleeing (Prusse 2022, 57). All the works concern resilience, perseverance, and hope in the face of hardship and distress. *When Stars Are Scattered* is the only autobiographical work of the five texts mentioned.

3.4.2 *When Stars Are Scattered*, a graphic memoir

The graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered* is considered a graphic memoir. Meltzer (2022) explains the difference between memoirs and autobiographies. Memoirs usually focus on one main incident or experience rather than the author's life, as autobiographies typically do. *When Stars Are Scattered* is a memoir because it recounts Omar Mohamed's story of living in the refugee camp instead of dealing with his whole life story. It is important to note that Omar Mohamed wrote his memoir with the help of the cartoonist Victoria Jamieson several years after his

time in the camp.

There are numerous types of memoirs, which can be written in prose or graphic narrations. This latter version of telling one's story has become more prevalent recently (Meltzer 2022). Although an author has many freedoms when writing one's memoir, a few main aspects should always be fulfilled. These include a specific theme, a critical situation the author had to overcome, using a first-person narrative voice, details, events, and people present at the time, a storyline with a plot and setting, and honesty (Meltzer 2022).

Graphic novel biographies or memoirs can be used in the ELT classroom to help students identify with the protagonist. The closeness to the story makes this person's life more graspable, and the images may add realism (Gavigan and Tomasevich 2011, 91). By making personal connections with characters of refugee narratives, students develop self-awareness about what influences their worldview and how they think about people and places (Penguin School and Library Marketing 2019).

3.5 Analysis of the graphic memoir *When Stars Are Scattered*

The following chapter provides a brief background on the authors and illustrators and a summary of the graphic novel's plot. Subchapter 3.5.1 examines the graphic memoir's suitability for the intended secondary school class. The visual and geographical aspects of the memoir will be analyzed in Subchapters 3.5.2 and 3.5.3, respectively, and ideas for their implementation are given in Subchapters 3.5.4.

The graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered*, a memoir by Omar Mohamed and Victoria Jamieson, recounts Omar's childhood at the refugee camp in Dadaab, Kenya. He had to flee from Somalia as a young boy, and after his father was killed and he was separated from his mother, he arrived at the camp with only his younger brother Hassan. He was later resettled to the United States of America and now lives in Pennsylvania with his wife and five children. He founded the non-profit Refugee Strong, which advocates for and supports students in refugee camps (National Book Foundation 2020). It is his original story that is depicted in

the graphic novel.

Victoria Jamieson is an American author who works as a book designer for HarperCollins Children's Books. She has written and illustrated several books, most about her life (Jamieson n.d.). She is responsible for the illustrations and fictionalized narrative of *When Stars Are Scattered*.

Iman Geddy, the colorist, is the third person to create this graphic novel. She is an African American illustrator with ancestral roots in Kenya, Somalia, and Ethiopia (Ms. Magazine n.d.).

The graphic novel tells the story of the former Somali refugee, Omar Mohamed, and his brother Hassan, who spent most of their childhood in a refugee camp in Kenya after fleeing the war in Somalia. The boys' father was killed, and they lost their mother on their way to Kenya. The novel describes the dull and strenuous life in Dadaab, the UN refugee camp. Omar, who is only eleven years old, struggles with taking care of his sick brother, not having enough to eat, and always waiting for food, resources, or a better life. When he is allowed to go to school and maybe change the brothers' future, Omar must decide whether to leave his brother, the only family he has left, every day or stay home and continue to care for him. The novel ends with the boys' resettlement to the United States of America (Jamieson and Mohamed 2020).

3.5.1 Age and gender appropriateness

The educator's guide for the graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered*, created by Penguin School and Library Marketing (2019), is designed for students grades 6-8, which aligns with what the School Library Journal suggests, advising the novel for students grade 4-8 (SLJ Staff 2020). This thesis's project and lesson plan, including the graphic novel, are outlined for 8th graders. Based on the protagonist's age and the suggested reading ages by Penguin School (2019) and the School Library Journal (2020), it might seem that the novel is not ideally suited for students in grade 8. Nevertheless, according to the educator's guide for the graphic novel, the story told in *When Stars Are Scattered* is relevant for all ages (Penguin School and Library Marketing 2019, 2). It allows readers to connect with

the residents of Dadaab and reflect on their struggles with loss and belonging (Penguin School and Library Marketing 2019, 2). Additionally, even though the main character is a boy, girls can identify with the story as several female characters appear and have a storyline. It shows that not only boys but also girls experience these hardships.

3.5.2 Visual analysis

The drawing style used by Victoria Jamieson in the graphic narration is notable as it uses a minimalist approach while still conveying the essential details and atmosphere.

Art: Even though the characters are not realistic, there is detail in the facial expressions. Looking at the characters' faces, it is immediately clear what emotions they are feeling. Feelings are, however, not only expressed through facial expressions but also with the colors used by the colorist. Red colors show anger, while blue provides a sense of calm. The novel's color palette differs depending on the situation and elements. Earthy tones and a limited range of colors show Dadaab's vast and dry landscape. The colorful clothing the refugees wear contrasts this and puts the focus on the characters rather than the background. It is possible to recognize the main characters through their clothing and their height, which stay the same throughout several chapters.

Because this drawing style is not overly realistic, it leaves much room for individual interpretation and imagination. It is, therefore, suitable for 7th or 8th grade students, as it is necessary to study the characters carefully to see all the details.

Font: The font in the graphic novel only uses capital letters. All letters are the same size and written in a sans-serif font. Sans-serif font is often viewed as modern, neutral, and emotionless (Adobe n.d.). The font was possibly chosen to give the images and the visuals around the text more weight. However, the boxes or balloons around the text and the thickness of the balloon outline or text provide more insight into the story's content. Spiked balloons or bold fonts indicate anger, while regular speech is in regular word balloons and non-bold writing.

Symbols: Symbols used in the narrative are stars, fences, water, and houses or homes. Stars are a recurring theme, first appearing in the title, shown throughout the novel, and lastly, as a symbol in the poem of the stars written by a student in Omar's class. Stars could represent dreams, hopes, and aspirations almost all the characters in the novel have. They could also stand for the brighter future Omar and his classmates strive for. The fence used to fence in the camp, and separate huts from each other could represent the obstacles and difficulties the characters face in the narrative. Water, a necessity of which there is never enough in the camp, is usually a symbol of life or cleansing. It could be the fresh start that Omar and his brother will receive later in the story. Lastly, the huts, shown at the beginning of every chapter, could symbolize Omar's longing for a place of belonging and safety.

Language: The language used in the graphic memoir is suitable for students at the secondary school level, as it uses regular everyday language use. For some L2 learners, words like 'foster mother' might be complex and need to be translated or explained. Often, the images can help students understand the text better.

Perspective and framing: Most panels are rectangular and restricted by black lines. However, some panels fill the whole page and sometimes even go beyond the page. The ones going on beyond the page appear endless and blend the space of the fictional world with the real world (Habegger-Conti 2021, 58, 60). Most borderless panels show the camp and thus express its incredible size, making it seem never-ending.

The perspectives used in this graphic narration are also notable. In most of the panels, it seems the reader is watching the story unfold before them. Several panels change perspective, such as the one where Omar receives the resettlement news. In this panel, the reader can see hands holding the letter, thus making it seem like the reader is Omar or at least in Omar's position.

3.5.3 Analysis of the geographical aspects

As mentioned in the chapter above, the story told by Omar Mohamed tells of his life in the refugee camp Dadaab. Since it is a graphic memoir, it is easy to think the events and actions in the novel can be taken as facts. This assumption is not entirely true, though, as the book is only based on Mohamed's experiences and was written and fictionalized by Victoria Jamieson. Omar was just eleven years old when he fled the civil war in Somalia and gave the input for the novel about ten years later. Understandably, not every conversation and detail in the book is represented as it was. Overall, however, the facts, places, and timeline of the story and the characters are real.

The refugee camp Dadaab, located in Kenya and very close to the Somali border, is a real place that can be found on a map. The location of the camp and its distance from Somalia is portrayed accurately in the novel. Kenya is bisected horizontally by the equator, with Dadaab north of it. In the northeastern part of Kenya, the climate is semiarid to arid. Although trees, grass, and water sources are limited, the area is not considered a desert. Most regions have an average temperature of 29° C or more (Ntarangwi, Ingham, and Hongo Ominde 2023). These characteristics are represented very clearly in the novel, as it is often mentioned how hot and dry it is. These aspects are essential for the project as they allow students to learn about Kenya's climate with the help of the novel and make inferences about life in these conditions. It also enables students to understand specific actions or events in the story.

Many African countries have a high migration rate due to war or conflict, persecution, poverty and hunger, natural catastrophes, environmental degradation, unemployment, or lack of educational opportunities (Heinrich Schoch et al. 2019). People suffering from these problems either move to a different place in their own country or flee to another country, often in Europe (Heinrich Schoch et al. 2019). People who flee to a place within their country are called internally displaced persons (Heinrich Schoch et al. 2019). Omar and his family are considered refugees because they leave their home country, Somalia, and escape to Kenya.

The political situation in Somalia is why an abundant number of people flee from there. The following history is based on Lewis (2023). Until 1991, Somalia was ruled by a military dictator, Said Barre, who was brutal and suppressed opponents. During his time as president of Somalia, rivalries between clans grew and became worse than they ever were before. In 1988, the situation was so dire that some groups attempted a government and military coup. The coup attempt led to the first Somali Civil War (1988-1991). Omar Mohamed was born around this time. Because of the fall of the president and the civil war, the country lacked a concrete government. Many different groups wanted to take power from 1991-2000. Several international groups wanted to help bring peace to Somalia, but nothing was successful. In the early 2000s, even after more than a million people died and hundreds fled to neighboring countries, Somalia still did not have one government. To this day, there are conflicts and disagreements about the government in Somalia (Lewis 2023). The graphic memoir does not mention these events explicitly, although the Somalia war is often mentioned. The events in Somalia are possibly not discussed in the novel because Omar did not know or understand them when he fled from Somalia and when he lived in the refugee camp. Additionally, these events were possibly not included in the novel to keep the narration age-appropriate and accessible to a young audience.

Somalia's most widely spread religion is Islam (Ntarangwi, Ingham, and Hongo Ominde 2023). This aspect is visible in the novel, as all the female characters wear hijabs. The traditions of Ramadan and Eid-Al Fitr, the holiday to celebrate the end of Ramadan, are also prominent aspects of the novel. Furthermore, one of the girl characters in the story is married off at a young age and is pregnant shortly after that. This situation also shows traditions most likely related to the family's religion.

3.5.4 Implementation in the project

Possible ways to use the visual aspects in class are to have specific lessons dedicated to emotions, perspectives, and framing. Emotions are significant in the novel and can be analyzed with colors, text, content, and font. It would be interesting to see which of the novel's elements help the students identify the emotions

and see if they can interpret them.

The perspectives used and the existing or non-existing panel frames are distinct in this novel and make a difference in how the reader perceives events. They also influence how much the reader is involved in the story. Through an analysis of these elements with students, they can gain more insight into what the authors tried to convey and study if or how this came across. Moreover, it familiarizes students with various tools to narrate their own stories and shape how their audience interprets a particular message.

From a geographical point of view, it could be interesting to look at different aspects of this novel. Firstly, localizing the refugee camp and Somalia is interesting to see how far the author traveled with his brother. Reading a map and localizing places are essential geography skills. In this context, it is also possible to analyze the weather and climate at the site of the camp to understand the hardships and the lifestyle choices better. In combination with the environment in Kenya, investigating the natural resources could help understand why Omar and the other refugees often do not have enough water or why there is no electricity.

Furthermore, the novel can help students find cultural and religious aspects of Somali culture. By analyzing the familial and neighborly structures in the refugee camp, students can learn about the cultural structures and habits of Somali people and the refugees in the camp. This analysis could help them compare their way of life to Omar's. Additionally, knowledge of the religion shown in the novel can help students understand the traditions and rituals established in the narrative.

3.6 Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL)

In Chapter 3.6, the objective is to establish the definition of CLIL in Subchapter 3.6.1, exhibit the application of CLIL within classrooms in Subchapter 3.6.2, and scrutinize the methodology in Subchapter 3.6.3. Additionally, the examination of the use of graphic narratives in a CLIL context is undertaken in Subchapter 3.6.4. Lastly, the implementation of CLIL in the project is proposed in Subchapter 3.6.5.

3.6.1 Definition of CLIL

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is an approach to teaching a language based on specific subjects (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 75). Its origins trace back to its introduction in Canada in 1960, where it was utilized to teach the other official language, French, to native English speakers. The idea was later embraced in Europe to enhance intercultural comprehension (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 76).

3.6.2 Implementing CLIL

Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann (2015, 75) explain that CLIL education predominantly occurs in a foreign language, albeit with the possibility of using the first language to explain concepts and learn subject-specific communication. However, merely employing a second language to teach a subject is not enough, as learners need to be aware of differences in conceptual understanding across different languages. For instance, 'friend' in American English encompasses a broader meaning than 'Freund' does in German. Hence, a part of CLIL involves language instruction and not just emphasis on the content (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 75).

The main principles for teaching with a CLIL approach concerning "content, cognition, communication, and culture" proposed by Mehisto et al. (referenced in Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 76) are:

- *"Double focus on academic and language learning*
- *Cross-curricular topics and projects*
- *Language across the curriculum*

- *Active, co-operative, task-based, and holistic learning*
- *Scaffolding [...]*
- *Development of concepts and skills in specific subjects [...]*
- *Comprehensible input and output, negotiation of meaning, routine discourse*
- *Authenticity in communication and materials*
- *Message before accuracy*
- *Media literacy*
- *Learner strategies to advance learner autonomy*
- *Raising awareness of language, cultural differences, and transcultural connections”.*

The Austrian researchers Reitbauer et al. (2018) focus on the importance of explicit language instruction in CLIL contexts. The argument for this is rooted in the idea that storing linguistic information in long-term memory is crucial for adequate language use. As specified by Roussel et al. (referenced in Reitbauer et al. 2018, 97), “neither listening nor speaking can be used effectively” “until that [linguistic] information has been stored in long-term memory”. They suggest explicit instruction supports this process by facilitating the storage of linguistic details in long-term memory, allowing students to comprehend and generate language more effectively. In the CLIL context, explicit instruction becomes essential for supporting second language learning. Otherwise, the working memory is overwhelmed with the language aspects and cannot take in the content information. Therefore, explicit language instruction while teaching content is inevitable (Reitbauer et al. 2018, 97).

3.6.3 Discussion of the method

Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann (2015, 77) list four objections to CLIL that skeptics have raised. The first is that the first language may suffer from being taught bilingually. Studies have shown that bilingually brought-up children lag behind their monolingually raised peers in language development. The second objection is that content knowledge or language learning may suffer from double focus. Thirdly, only a small elite part of learners benefit from CLIL, possibly because it is cognitively demanding to learn content and language simultaneously.

Lastly, the teachers may not be adequately equipped with language and or content knowledge as well as material to reach the expectations of bilingual teaching.

The first three objections mentioned have mainly been overcome. According to Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann (2015, 77), young bilingual learners may have a smaller vocabulary in one language but a much larger one when combining the two languages. Additionally, variations in language development exist in monolingual learners as well. Further, dealing more in-depth with the subject matter to find appropriate concepts and words in the second language fosters a greater cognitive depth of processing. This process, therefore, leads to a positive effect on cognitive development. Lastly, bilingual teaching may help immigrant students with a lower language proficiency in the country's first language. They start on the same level as native children, and the gap between learners of different backgrounds can be minimized.

The last criticized aspect mentioned above is valid for various teachers. It is not easy for teachers to find CLIL material for language learners. The teacher's language proficiency in a specific subject is also not always given (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 78). Using graphic novels in the ELT classroom may provide a possible solution to this problem. They give the teachers material and help them with the vocabulary to discuss the matter. Of course, preparation concerning language competence, lesson preparation, and intense familiarization with the subject is of the essence.

Nevertheless, the benefits of the CLIL method surpass the presented criticism (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 78). The technique enhances awareness in first and second languages, improves language skills through implicit and explicit instruction, and inspires motivation with authentic materials (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 78). Therefore, versions or phases of CLIL should be implemented in English and domain-specific subject-teaching classrooms (Grimm, Meyer, and Volkmann 2015, 78).

3.6.4 Using graphic narratives in CLIL

Josué Llull examined using the graphic narration *The Adventures of Tintin* to produce quality output in social sciences in a CLIL approach (Llull 2014). This chapter gives an overview of how to use the activities he devised. The activities Llull designed can be generalized for using graphic novels in CLIL.

Llull (2014, 53) differentiated between “language focused activities [soft CLIL] and content focused [hard CLIL] activities”. The language-focused activities included using the graphic narration for scaffolding techniques, communication activities, forums concerning “reading in detail, analysing, commenting on and discussing each comic book in order to foster literacy” (Llull 2014, 53), and learning English idioms. The content-focused activities included those about geography and history and those associated with social and cultural aspects.

Scaffolding techniques. The activities summarized under this term focused mainly on describing, analyzing, and commenting on graphic narrations. In addition, Llull (2014, 54) used tasks like

meeting the characters of the comic in a short performance, wearing costumes, projecting selected cartoons on a digital whiteboard, decorating the classroom, showing handcrafted materials related to the comic, providing mysterious clues about the comic’s plot, asking questions, and guessing the topic to work on.

These activities aimed to “introduce [...] concepts, specific vocabulary, and language structures”, which would later help students understand the content-focused activities (Llull 2014, 54).

Communication activities. These activities centered around students using graphic narrations as a basis for informal conversations about it. The pictures in the strips help to understand “the meaning of language expressions” (Llull 2014, 55) and the plot. Two examples of this type of activity are describing single panels with scaffolds given by the teacher or filling in blank speech bubbles.

All tasks centered around the communication activities involved the three steps of

CLIL, namely “*language of learning* ([...] analysis of content [...]), *language for learning* ([...] structures and discourse patterns [that can be transferred]), *language through learning* ([...] knowledge that comes [through the activities])” (Lull 2014, 55).

Forums. The activities in this group focused on “reading in detail, analyzing, commenting on, and discussing [graphic narrations] to foster literacy” (Lull 2014, 55). The idea was that students talk about the language and images to fully understand the plot and the interactions between the characters (Lull 2014, 55).

Activities to learn English idioms. Since the texts in graphic narrations are very close to authentic language use, they are a great way to teach idioms and expressions. The visuals can help understand the regular text and the idioms used in English (Lull 2014, 56).

The content-focused activities in the *Tintin Project* (Lull 2014, 56) included activities related to geography, history, social, and cultural aspects.

Geography. In the *Tintin Project*, several activities focused on tracking Tintin’s movements on a map. However, this is not the only way to combine geography with graphic narrations. It is also possible to compare photographs of landscapes to the depiction in the panels or infer the characteristics of ecosystems through the way they are drawn (Lull 2014, 56-57).

History. Since history can be a complex subject to teach in a foreign language, mainly because students may be missing the vocabulary to talk about it adequately, the activities proposed by Lull (2014, 57) focus primarily on contextualizing the plot of the graphic narration in its historical background. The next step can be to compare the depiction of the historical event in the novel to facts found through research fostering critical comparisons.

Social aspects. These activities aimed to show “social situations, lifestyles, and economic activities appearing in the comics” (Lull 2014, 58). These situations can then be analyzed critically and show students the reasons for revolutions, the negative

consequences of illegal forms of trade, or elements as simple as hobbies and leisure activities.

Cultural aspects. The Tintin graphic narrations specifically, but many other comics also show “a variety of ethnic groups, cultural traditions, religions, customs, languages, behaviors, and festivities” (Llull 2014, 58). This group's activities focused on identifying and analyzing these aspects.

3.6.5 Implementation in the project

Implementing CLIL into the project of this thesis can be done with the elements proposed by Llull (2014). The ideas can be divided into soft and hard CLIL aspects. Soft CLIL activities are language-focused, while hard CLIL activities are content-focused. One possible soft CLIL activity is to give students the novel's title page and have them guess what the book could be about. This activity introduces essential vocabulary that will later be used in the hard CLIL activities. Another approach could be to give students a recent image of refugees and have them describe what they see and feel. This method again allows them to acquire the necessary vocabulary and language structures and introduce the topic of forcible migration to them.

A hard CLIL activity in the project could be to have students compare photographs of landscapes in Kenya or the refugee camp Dadaab with the depiction in the graphic novel. Through this comparison, inferences on the climate and the landscape can be made. It is also possible to integrate Somalia's history into the project so that students understand why Omar and his brother had to flee their home country. This action contextualizes the plot for the students. Furthermore, the social situations and lifestyles depicted in the novel can be analyzed, which can give students insight into why characters act or behave in specific ways. Lastly, the cultural aspects of life in the refugee camp, like religion, traditions, or customs, can be examined.

3.7 Cross-curricular teaching

This chapter explains cross-curricular teaching and details its history in Subchapter 3.7.1. The challenges of this method are explored in Subchapter 3.7.2. Implementing this teaching form and its localization in Curriculum 21 is the focus of Subchapters 3.7.3 and 3.7.4. Lastly, a link between cross-curricular teaching and CLIL is established in Subchapter 3.7.5.

The cross-curricular teaching and learning approach is often heard in combination with terms like interdisciplinary, integrated learning, thematic approach or work, project work, or project-based learning (Xerri Hili and Schembri 2022, 232; Kelly 2013, 3). The cross-curricular approach and other related terms all focus on simultaneously applying skills and competencies from both subjects, thus enhancing the student's development (Xerri Hili and Schembri 2022, 232; Kelly 2013, 3-4). However, cross-curricular teaching is not limited to two subjects but links several subjects, although it is crucial to reduce the number to have a clear focus for the students (Kelly 2013, 4). Next, a brief history of cross-curricular teaching will be given. The challenges associated with this method and how to implement it in the classroom will be analyzed afterward.

3.7.1 History of cross-curricular teaching

The cross-curricular teaching approach is not new (Kelly 2013, 1). The Plowden Report of the Central Advisory Council for Education into Primary Education in England stated in 1967 that children do not learn in subject categories but in broad areas (Kelly 2013, 1). Carr (referenced in Kelly 2013, 2) also argues that knowledge is interrelated, which is often seen as a justification for cross-curricular teaching. However, according to Kelly (2013, 2), the report did not consider that "some discrete subject teaching" is essential for children older than early primary school age. Since the beginning of the 2000s, there seemed to be a shift towards cross-curricular approaches in several curriculums, such as Scotland's, Northern Ireland's, and New Zealand's (Kelly 2013, 3) and the new Swiss curriculum. In this curriculum, the two subjects, geography and history, have been merged to encourage cross-curricular learning, among other reasons.

3.7.2 Challenges of cross-curricular teaching

If cross-curricular teaching were the ideal and easiest way of teaching, all schools and curricula would implement it immediately. However, this is not the case because challenges are associated with this method, as with any given approach. It should, however, be mentioned that according to Xerri Hili and Schembri (2022, 237-238), the literature predominantly addresses the drawbacks of this approach by highlighting teachers' apprehensions and concerns rather than providing specific criticisms of the method.

One reason against using a cross-curricular approach is the careful planning and development it requires (Kelly 2013, 8). Kelly (2013, 8) points out that several teachers have not learned how to implement cross-curricular work in their studies and are reluctant to execute this approach. Another challenge when using the cross-curricular method is the balance of the two subjects (Kelly 2013, 8). However, Laurie (referenced in Kelly 2013, 9) notes that having one lead subject may sometimes be beneficial. A third obstacle mentioned by Kelly (2013, 9) when implementing cross-curricular work is assessment. The author states that traditional assessment forms are only partly sensible as most focus on assessing subject-specific knowledge. These forms leave out how students apply the knowledge which is vital in cross-curricular teaching.

3.7.3 Implementing cross-curricular teaching

Even considering the challenges mentioned above, cross-curricular teaching should still be considered in teaching. One reason for using the approach is that students use actual insights from different subject disciplines to solve problems, which simulates real life where students will have to apply skills learned in other subjects in their future careers (Kelly 2013, 7). Xerri Hili and Schembri (2022, 232) elaborate on this by explaining that a school's curriculum needs to facilitate learning 21st-century skills and critical competencies. According to the two authors, the "curriculum must be contextual [...] and cross-curricular to teach knowledge and competences [...]" (Xerri Hili and Schembri 2022, 232). Kelly (2013, 7) also adds that cross-curricular work can help with motivation and en-

agement, as the topics to be learned are placed in a relevant context. Furthermore, students with different interests can engage in the topic as it involves more than one subject.

3.7.4 Cross-curricular teaching in Curriculum 21

Teaching in a cross-curricular way plays a significant role in Curriculum 21 in cycles one and two, meaning elementary school (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017). Cycle three is mainly used to teach sustainable development across different subjects. Nevertheless, the basics of the curriculum highlight the potential of working in a cross-curricular way to show the multiple layers of complex topics and make connections and interplay between topics understandable. The various perspectives on one topic can show that some views only show parts of reality (Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich 2017).

3.7.5 Linking cross-curricular teaching to CLIL

Based on the above definitions and implementations of the two methods, cross-curricular teaching and CLIL, it can be deduced that they are similar in several ways and can, therefore, be linked. The following reflection is based on the subchapters concerning the two teaching methods. Both approaches are interdisciplinary and thus emphasize the interconnectedness of knowledge and skills across disciplines. This skill will be necessary for numerous careers later in life. Additionally, both methods aim to enhance learning outcomes by providing a more holistic educational experience rather than teaching a topic isolated in one subject. CLIL supports a deeper understanding of subject matter and language skills by integrating language learning with content instruction. Cross-curricular teaching aims to deepen understanding by linking different subjects and fostering connections between various concepts. Moreover, both approaches help students develop cultural awareness. CLIL often exposes students to different cultural perspectives through the content studied and the language used, primarily because authentic material is used. Cross-curricular activities may also incorporate cultural elements when looking at topics from various disciplines, thereby promoting cultural awareness and sensitivity.

4 Method

This chapter explains the research method and justifies the data collection procedure, which is done by describing the participants in Chapter 4.1 and explaining the tools used to collect the data in Chapter 4.2. Additionally, the qualitative content analysis of qualitative data in Chapter 4.3 and the quantitative analysis of qualitative data in Chapter 4.4 will be distinguished (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022).

Qualitative data is diverse and can span from text to images to audio (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 16). Therefore, various methods are proposed to analyze this data (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 19-20). Kuckartz and Rädiker (2022, 32) suggest that adopting methodological strictness in qualitative data analysis is essential for establishing it as an accepted, respected, and verifiable research method within the research community. Their definition of the qualitative content analysis, "systematische und methodisch kontrollierte wissenschaftliche Analyse von Texten, Bildern, Filmen und anderen Inhalten von Kommunikation" (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 39) puts categories, to code the collected data relevant to the research question, in the center of the analysis. Categories can be defined deductively, inductively, or a mix of both. The analysis is usually qualitative but can also contain quantitative-statistical analyses (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 39).

The qualitative research method was chosen for this research project because students' attitudes and individual development were the focus of this thesis. Quantitative data would not do the students' responses and subjective perceptions justice. Even with the strictness in methodology, the qualitative research method leaves room for the interpretation of the answers and allows for an adaptation of the categories while exploring the material (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022).

4.1 Participants

The following chapter describes and justifies the sample students chosen for this project. The study was conducted with a class of twenty-three Swiss EFL second-year secondary school students at a public secondary school in the canton of Zurich in Switzerland. The school uses regular classrooms for input lessons and teaches students independence with individually organized work in a shared office space.

The class was selected for convenience, as it was, due to scheduling conflicts, not possible for the author of this thesis to teach the planned lessons herself. A competent native English-speaking teacher who teaches geography and English was chosen to teach the prepared plan to her class.

The class that was taught the prepared lesson plan was a second-year secondary school class. The teacher has had this class for the past year and has just started the new school year with them. The class consisted of twenty-three students (twelve boys and eleven girls), several of whom speak English at home. Two students grew up in Switzerland and have one American English- and one German-speaking parent. One girl lived in New Zealand until age eight and thus still speaks English to both parents. One girl is Swiss with Swiss parents, but they speak English to her at home. The students mentioned above, as well as one Spanish- and one German-speaking student with an extremely high level of English, took an extra English course in the past year. Apart from the New Zealander and the two Ukrainian refugees, all students have been learning English since the third grade. Based on the curriculum (Zürich 2017), the students should be on an A2.1-2 level in English, compared to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). The teacher, however, estimates her class to be on a level closer to B1 and some even B2.

Nevertheless, some students are weaker than others. According to the teacher, one student has a deficient level, two are not very strong, and the two Ukrainian refugees have a much lower level of English than their peers, as their

English level at school is significantly lower than in Switzerland. The teacher indicated that most students are especially good at listening and speaking tasks, whereas writing is difficult for many. They are often missing the correct grammatical structures to make their writing proficient, but their texts are nevertheless understandable for the most part.

According to the teacher, the class read the first Harry Potter book together in the first year of secondary school. Some parts were read individually, some were read out loud, and some were listened to from an audiobook. Few students read some parts in German. Several students read English books in their free time as well.

The teacher has never explicitly worked on intercultural competencies with the students before. As a “religion and ethics” teacher, she has incorporated empathy in this class or used listening and reading tasks in English to focus on cultures.

How the teacher divided the lessons between the scheduled subjects was left up to her. She planned to use four weeks to teach the whole plan, which included an activity booklet. Because the teacher is experienced and it should be made as easy as possible for her to lead the prepared project, it was left up to her which lessons she would teach as input lessons and which ones she would leave for her students to work on in the shared office space. For the teacher to be as flexible as possible and have enough material, all lessons were planned as direct teaching lessons.

4.2 Data collection

This chapter explains the instrument used to collect the data, i.e., the lesson plan and activity booklet. Based on the theoretical background of Chapter 2, a lesson plan was written to develop secondary students’ intercultural competencies. The lesson plan uses the graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered* (Mohamed and Jamieson 2020) and the geography teaching book *Weltsicht* (Heinrich Schoch et al. 2019) to engage students in activities that will hopefully arouse their curiosity

for learning about a new culture, increase their knowledge about migration in Africa, refugee camps and the main character's Somali culture, heighten their cultural awareness, develop their skill of comparing, interpreting and relating to different cultures, and teach them to ask questions and reflect on values and beliefs.

In the first of about ten lessons, students were introduced to the graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered* and the topic of migration. Next, the novel was put into its historical and geographical context. Since students could not read the entire story due to time shortage, they were given a short plot overview. In lesson four, students studied what life in a refugee camp, especially Dadaab, is like. Following this lesson, identity wheels for the author Omar Mohamed and each student were created to find similarities between the teenagers. In the next class, the ESL learners were encouraged to learn how the framing and positioning choices of graphic narration authors and cartoonists influence the amount of involvement a reader feels. Next, the activities focused on reflection on the culture of the people in the narration and allowed students to compare their findings with their own culture. In the last lesson, students learned how emotions can be expressed through colors, text, and facial expressions in a graphic narration. The novel's conclusion allowed students to compare what they read to their lives and explain the powerful sentence, "No one chooses to become a refugee." The last lesson included a table of statements in which students could reflect on their learning development compared to the first lesson. The complete lesson plan can be found in the appendix (*Appendix A: Lesson plan*).

In combination with the lesson plan, students worked on an activity booklet during the lessons. There were both closed-ended and open-ended questions for students to answer, all to be answered in written form. Having the answers written down was the only way the data could be analyzed, as the researcher of this thesis was not present in the lessons.

The first part of the booklet collected data on the students' preconceptions and their prior knowledge of the aimed to be taught, the middle part sought to develop students' skills, knowledge, attitudes, and values, and the final part posed

the same questions as the first, to see a possible shift in conceptions and expertise. The first and last parts consisted mainly of closed-ended questions, while the middle parts were primarily open-ended. The activities in the booklet were adopted and adapted from the geography curriculum student's book and workbook *Weltsicht* (Heinrich Schoch et al. 2019), the activity guide from the book *When Stars Are Scattered* (Mohamed and Jamieson 2020), and from several suggestions made by authors who researched developing IC in students.

4.3 Qualitative content analysis of qualitative data

A qualitative content analysis, based on Kuckartz and Rädiker (2022), was conducted to analyze the data collected in the open-ended tasks in the activity booklet, and their seven steps were followed. Before analyzing the data, students' answers to the tasks were typed up and edited for spelling and clarity without modifications to the meaning. In the *first step*, according to Kuckartz and Rädiker (2022, 132-133), the data was looked at, the content was explored, and seemingly essential parts were marked. Any ideas concerning the later analysis were noted in memos. Tasks not relevant to answering the research question were dropped.

In the *second step*, the main categories for coding the material were defined (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 61, 133). These main categories were deductively derived from the research question (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 63) and were defined before the analysis. In this case, they were *visual*, *text-based*, *cultural*, and *geographical* elements. The categories were entered into a code frame in an Excel list. The code frame can be found in the appendix as part of the code book (*Appendix B: Code book Excel*).

Kuckartz and Rädiker (2022, 134) defined the main categories as a search pattern to explore the data in the *third step*. The matching text in the responses was sorted into the corresponding main lists. The goal was to code all the essential text parts and match the answers to the main categories (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 67-68).

Following Kuckartz and Rädiker's *fourth step* (2022, 138), subcategories were formed inductively. All four main categories were divided into subcategories and

defined by examining the data and finding the need for new categories. The code frame was then expanded to include the coding definitions to form the code book (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 66). The created code book was entered into Excel and can be found in the appendix (*Appendix B: Code book Excel*).

The data was reviewed in the *fifth step*, and the previously defined text parts were matched to the new subcategories (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 142). Additionally, anchor examples were selected and entered into the code book.

According to Kuckartz and Rädiker (2022, 147), the *sixth step* is to analyze the coded material. The authors offer eight different analyses, some more complex than others. In this thesis, the category-based analysis along the main categories was chosen. This form sorts the results along the main categories and presents the content of the results qualitatively, meaning that similarities, differences, and notable aspects are mentioned. Anchor examples are given here (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 147-148).

According to the authors, the *seventh* and final *step* is writing down the results, the findings, and the answer to the research question and documenting how the analysis was done. The process should be documented and explained (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 154-155).

4.4 Quantitative analysis of qualitative data

At the beginning and the end of the activity booklet, students were asked to decide if they agreed or disagreed with certain statements. These answers can be considered qualitative data but were analyzed quantitatively in contrast to the open-ended questions from the qualitative content analysis. The author's example for this kind of analysis is evaluating the number of times a word or word combination was used (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022, 17). In the context of this thesis, the number of times students checked agree and disagree were counted. These numbers were then summarized in a bar graph in Chapter 5.2. The bar diagram (*figure 4*) shows the number of times students chose a particular answer.

5 Results

This chapter summarizes the results gathered from the qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data. The qualitative results will be presented in Chapter 5.1, while the quantitative results will be outlined in Chapter 5.2.

5.1 Qualitative analysis results

The categories for the qualitative analysis were based on the research question. This subchapter is, therefore, organized along the main categories used to code the students' responses.

5.1.1 Visual aspects of the graphic novel

The students' answers referring to the visual elements of the graphic novel *When Stars Are Scattered* were analyzed to examine how the youth utilized the elements to enhance their understanding of the novel. The full answers to all of the relevant questions can be found in the appendix (*Appendix C: Answers from the students' activity booklets*).

Students were able to interpret colors used in specific chapters to understand characters' emotions: *"red: sad and angry, red mostly represents anger so it's used to show Omar's anger"* as well as the atmosphere portrayed by the cartoonist: *"colors are gray, dark blue, dark green. It makes like a hopeless and sad atmosphere"*.

Not only were the colors crucial to understanding the characters' emotions, but also the facial expressions carefully drawn by the cartoonist. Almost all the students could quickly identify sadness: *"sad because of the tears"* and happiness: *"happy: smile on his face."* Additionally, one student recognized the emotion of exhaustion: *"[...] and exhaustion. [...] most of the faces are [in] the hands [...] to wash the tears away"*.

The students gained new knowledge about the refugee camp through specific drawings by the cartoonist. Numerous insights were about soccer: *"If they want to play soccer they have to make a ball out of trash bags"* or *"In this camp it has a dirty field for the kids to play football on [...]"*. Furthermore, students learned

about the appearance of the camp: *"In the camp it's sandy and everywhere is sand [...]"* or *"The streets are dirty because there is a lot of trash on the floor."* Lastly, new knowledge on life in the refugee camp was acquired: *"They also lack some basic necessities that we take for granted like public transport or a good school. In the book we saw three kids at one desk"*.

Lastly, students could make interpretations based on the visuals in the novel. They made assumptions about the book by looking at the cover page: *"I think this book is about two friends that live in Africa. In the picture of this book I can see trees from Africa."* Similarly, several students understood the cartoonists' perspective choices: *"[...] view of the people but of the whole situation. That these people are lonely on this ocean."*

5.1.2 Text-based aspects of the graphic novel

One of the main differences between graphic narratives and regular books in prose is the combination of visuals and text. For this reason, students' answers were analyzed on how they used textual aspects to understand the novel better.

Very few students used text in the novel to understand emotions and feelings: *"sad, because of his word choice."* The interpretations of emotions and feelings made using the text were very general: *"He starts to feel angry, annoyed and sad [...] because how he acts around other people, he started to push them away"*.

Many traditions that came up in the novel were described in words. Almost all the students referred to the tradition of Ramadan and Eid Al-Fitr: *"Celebrate the end of Ramadan with Eid Al-Fitr, a big holiday."* A few students also mentioned storytelling: *"[...] telling each other stories"* and traditions around the celebrations *"[...] if they have a celebration, they buy new ones [clothes], if they have enough money"*.

The students gained meaningful insights into refugee camps using the text in the novel. Most of the knowledge referred to the food and water rations: *"In the first 10 days you have a lot of food, but the last 5 days they don't have enough food"*

and all the people are very angry". Waiting was repeatedly mentioned: "[...] waiting, waiting for food, water, help". Several students also showed they gained new knowledge on education in Dadaab: *"They don't have enough supplies and a long way to go to school."*

5.1.3 Geographical aspects of the graphic novel

When working with the graphic novel's geographical aspects, the tasks often focused the students' attention on them. Nevertheless, the students could capture Kenya's climate very well and compare it to the environment in Switzerland. They also learned the reasons why people flee from their home countries.

Students accurately summarized Kenya's climate as: *"hot, dry, very sunny."* Some students also concluded, *"It seems like it doesn't rain often there. By looking at the picture Kenya looks more like a big desert"*.

Only a few students could refer to Kenya's climate's consequences on the inhabitants of Dadaab. These were, however, deducted correctly: *"dress [the way they do] because it's hot."*

Many students could compare the climate in Kenya to the one in Switzerland: *"A difference would be the climate because in Kenya it's much dryer and hotter than in Switzerland."* Some students even explained the consequences of the different climates: *"If there was a refugee camp in Switzerland, I think there wouldn't be tents because in winter here it gets very cold, and tents wouldn't be warm."*

The last geographic aspect of focus in the activity booklet was why people fled from their homelands. Students noted reasons like: *"1. Resource crisis, such as a shortage of food and water. 2. War reasons"* and *"People leave their home also because of natural catastrophes like fire or tsunami [...]"*.

5.1.4 Cultural aspects of the graphic novel

The cultural aspects of the GN were measured by analyzing if students can put themselves in others' situations, have knowledge of cultural practices in Somali culture, can explain and interpret religion in Somali culture, and find similarities

and differences between aspects of life in a refugee camp and aspects of students' own lives.

There was an abundant number of answers showing that the students can put themselves in the situation of a refugee in a refugee camp: *"If I would be in Omar's place I would be sad and live without a mom is hard. I'm going to feel so bad."* They also showed that they can put themselves in the situation of a fleeing refugee: *"I feel happy for a new life and sad because I have to go from my old life. I am scared because the sea is dangerous."*

Students mainly learned about cultural practices relating to religion in Somali culture: *"I think all of the women have headscarves on. They celebrate Ramadan and Eid Al-Fitr"*. Multiple answers also specified certain practices concerning the holiday Eid Al-Fitr: *"They celebrate and pray together. After they prayed they have candy on Eid Al-Fitr"*.

Furthermore, students could explain and interpret religion in Somali culture: *"They are Muslim and religion is very important to them. They all got together for praying and celebrating"*.

Lastly, most similarities referred to hobbies and school: *"We both go to school"* and *"We both like to play football."* One student added that Omar and he *"both like to spend time with our brothers."* Another similarity was that the children in the graphic novel and the students: *"have to help in the household."*

Many differences between the two living styles were found and outweigh the similarities. Most of the differences referred to education: *"They also have a school but it's not the same like we have. They don't have the equipment like us"*. Another aspect often mentioned was the clothing: *"[...] difference is that they wear all day the same clothes and they can't buy new clothes. I have so many clothes to wear and when one has a hole or something I can buy new ones"*. Furthermore, food and water were often mentioned as a difference: *"In my life I can eat when and what I want, but in the graphic novel it's like you get all days/weeks food and not much."* Additional differences referred to religion: *"They also have different*

religions (I don't have one)," housing: "In Switzerland there would be a house, whereas in Kenya there is a tent," electronic gadgets: "You don't have [...] with computers, papers and pens, the internet for your handy and electric things", and routine: "in a refugee camp people are having the same daily routine every day, compared to mine I can choose and plan the day the way I want."

5.2 Quantitative analysis results

In the table, more students agreed with the statements "I can imagine what life in a refugee camp may be like," "I can empathize with the difficulties of people who have to leave their country," "I know about the situation of refugees," and "I am curious about other cultures" after working through the lesson plan than before. For the statement "I can read a graphic novel," the same number of students agreed before and after. Sixteen students decided, "I can use the images and colors in a graphic novel to understand feelings and emotions," before working through the tasks. After the lessons, only fifteen students agreed with the statement. Lastly, twelve students agreed with "I have nothing in common with refugees" before the study, while only seven agreed after the project. The results are summarized in a graph (figure 4). Agreeing is the preferred answer for all but one of the statements. The desirable response to the statement "I have nothing in common with refugees" is to disagree.

Figure 4: Bar graph showing students' self-assessment regarding seven statements. The data shown was collected for this project.

6 Discussion

This thesis aims to answer how the visual, text-based, geographical, and cultural aspects of the graphic memoir *When Stars Are Scattered* in a CLIL (content and language integrated learning) setting influence students' intercultural competence. Chapter 6.1 summarizes and discusses the results of the four critical aspects defined in the research question and interprets them in the context of the theoretical basis established in Chapter 3. The implications and limitations of the results are then considered in Chapters 6.2 and 6.3.

6.1 Key findings and interpretation

The quantitative data from the table, where students were asked to express agreement or disagreement with a statement, indicates that overall, most students evaluated themselves more positively post-study than pre-study. After the lessons, more students agreed with statements about understanding and empathy towards refugees and different cultures. This result can be explained through the qualitative answers, which showed that students gained knowledge through the instructional plan and reading the graphic novel. They possibly decided they understood a different culture more because of the new knowledge. The number of students who agreed to be able to read a graphic novel remained the same before and after. This result is likely because students had read visual narrations before this project and were confirmed in their belief that they can read graphic novels by understanding this novel. Notably, fewer students agreed to be able to interpret feelings and emotions using images in a graphic novel after the lesson. It is imaginable that the first decision was based on students having already read visual narrations before and thinking they could use their experiences of human faces to understand how a character is feeling in the novel. Students potentially realized through the work with the story that it is not always possible to transfer real-life interpretation skills to a graphic narration. They may have learned that more than just facial expressions play into portraying a character's emotions. Fewer students believed they had nothing in common with refugees after the study. This positive outcome could be explained through the task where students had to find similarities between themselves and Omar, a refugee. Through this realization, they likely

understood that there are certain aspects they can have in common with refugees.

The qualitative data allows for a more detailed analysis of the four aspects used to develop intercultural competence. The visual elements of the graphic memoir facilitated the understanding of the content, the character's emotions, and an interpretation thereof, compared to text-based literature. Through this, the students gained a deeper awareness and empathy for the characters in the book and, thus, the hardships they faced in a refugee camp. These aspects show that with the visuals, students improved their intercultural competence in *savoir* (knowledge) and *savoir comprendre* (interpreting and relating). The results clearly showed that visuals played a prominent role for the students. This realization supports the choice of graphic narrations for this project, as students might not have understood these aspects if the novel had been purely text-based. Since students correctly interpreted and used the visual elements, it shows they possess visual literacy, which, according to several authors, is crucial in today's world (Eisenmann 2022, 58-60; Prusse 2022, 56; Gillenwater 2009, 33; Burmark 2008, 6).

Students used the text far less than the imagery in their development of IC. Nevertheless, text was the primary source of new knowledge students learned about refugee camps and for their understanding of traditions in Somali and refugee culture. It was also the aspect that gave students the content-specific vocabulary needed to reply to the tasks. Relating the text-based aspect to IC, they helped the students with *savoir* (knowledge). Maybe students used the text less than the images due to a lack of vocabulary or simply because understanding images is inherently more natural to them than text. As the researchers Gultom, Frans, and Cellay (2022, 52) and Bakar, Ahmad, and Yunus (2020, 44) explained, images help weaker students understand the text better. Thus, students may have believed they used the drawings more than the text. It is also possible students used the text more implicitly in their development of IC but did not mention it explicitly in their answers, thus making it impossible to deduce.

The geographical aspects of the graphic novel were practically never men-

tioned in tasks that did not explicitly ask for geographical answers. Even so, students were able to use them to gain knowledge about the refugee camp's location in Kenya and about why people are forced to flee from their homelands. These tasks gave them background knowledge on why people live in refugee camps and explained why refugees cannot return to their previous lives. Although geography helped students increase their knowledge (*savoir*), it seems that students used it very little to develop their IC. Again, geographical knowledge possibly influenced the students' answers, showing their intercultural competence, but since it was not mentioned explicitly, it is not possible to know to what extent.

Culture is an essential aspect of intercultural competence. However, which specific culture students should learn about is not uniformly defined. Some tasks and responses focused on Somali culture, while others concentrated on refugee culture. This umbrella term is used because it is difficult to differentiate between the two. Students significantly improved their *savoir comprendre* (interpreting and relating) with the cultural tasks. They could interpret traditions, ways of life, and actions from the studied culture and compare them to their own culture.

Additionally, students improved their *savoir être* (intercultural attitudes) through the tasks that were focused on the cultural aspects of the GN. Students showed that they valued the attitudes and beliefs of others by not judging the actions of the book's characters and trying to find explanations for their acts or emotions. They mostly achieved this by comparing how they would feel in a particular situation with how the characters felt. Through the close study and exploration of the cultures shown in the graphic memoir, the students improved their *savoir apprendre/faire* (discovery and interaction) and their *savoir* (knowledge). These results suggest that the cultural aspects had the most significant influence on students' intercultural competencies development.

6.2 Implications

The fact that various students used visual aspects of the novel for an improved understanding of the content and to acquire new knowledge about the life described in the novel supports Gultom, Frans, and Cellay's (2022, 46) statement that this type of literature helps students overcome vocabulary and grammatical awareness barriers. Gillenwater (2009, 33) also stated that graphic narrations, specifically graphic novels, are the ideal medium for teaching visual literacy. Since students used the visuals in the novel intensely and correctly, Gillenwater's statement can also be confirmed. The implication in verifying these two theories is that graphic novels and the focus on the visual aspects should continue to be used in school to develop students' visual literacy and improve their understanding of the narration's content.

The quantitative results on students' attitudes and curiosity toward a different culture and the qualitative results on students' ability to put themselves in the situation of a refugee in a refugee camp fit with the theory by Thaler (2016, 24) that using a text from a different country, in this case Kenya and somewhat the United States as the narration was written there, may lead students to be more open and tolerant toward other cultures. Likewise, students comparing their own lives to that of the protagonist fits with Thaler's (2016, 70) theory that students receive the chance to experience different ways of life through literature and are thus forced to compare them to their own. Moreover, looking at the change in the quantitative results from before and after the study, Thaler's (2016,70) idea that this comparison can lead to more curiosity about other cultures can be confirmed. The confirmation of Thaler's findings through this research project should be considered when deciding which narrations, specifically from which origin, should be read and what kind of activities should be done in class.

Even though multiple students found several similarities between themselves and the protagonist, as well as their lives and the one represented in the story, the results do not entirely fit Wang and Donovan's (2020) theory that a type of 'we' thinking can be established through highlighting similarities between the

cultures and specific individuals. The quantitative results showed that several students still do not think they have anything in common with refugees, even after completing the lesson plan and activity booklet. This result contributes to a clearer understanding that a change or development does not happen automatically in students but must instead be explicitly focused on. Additionally, it is vital to work on intercultural competencies more than once so that all students can find similarities between themselves and individuals from a different culture, thus seeing the group and themselves as more of a 'we.'

6.3 Limitations

Even though some conclusions could be drawn from the results analyzed, it is essential to note that the number of activity booklets collected limits the generalization of the results. The study reviewed the answers of eighteen students in one school. It is, therefore, impossible to be sure if the same conclusions would have been drawn had this project been performed in a different school or with more students.

Another limitation of this study is that the researcher did not teach the lessons herself. Therefore, some responses were missing, and some tasks were solved differently than expected. Also, it is not possible to gauge how much input or help was given by the teacher for the students to be able to solve the tasks. If the researcher had taught the lessons herself, she would be able to take her input and assistance into consideration when evaluating the results.

It was beyond the scope of this study for students to read the entire novel. Each task required students to read a few pages in the book on which they based their answers. Had the whole novel been read, the students would most likely have had more background knowledge and could have gained more detailed insight into the life shown in the narrative. This more detailed understanding might have influenced their responses.

A further limitation can be seen in the fact that no tasks developed students' *savoir s'engager*. These skills can be improved best with role-plays or real-life interactions. As mentioned in Chapter 4.2, it was beyond the scope of this study to

implement these skills in the lesson plan because the researcher of this thesis needed written answers to analyze since she was not present during the lessons. Hence, enhancing students' intercultural competencies could also be achieved by emphasizing these skills.

Lastly, a limitation of this study is that it is impossible to know the exact level of intercultural competence the students had before working on the novel. The pre-reading table, the basis of the quantitative results, is an insight into students' attitudes before the lessons. It does not, however, fully capture students' pre-knowledge and attitudes and does not make it explicit which graphic novel elements were responsible for acquiring new knowledge and attitude changes.

7 Conclusion

This chapter gives a conclusion on the research by restating the main findings. Chapter 7.1 reflects on the procedure used in this thesis. Finally, the consequences for teaching and an outlook into further possible research are presented in Chapter 7.2.

This research aimed to identify how the visual, text-based, geographical, and cultural elements of the graphic memoir *When Stars Are Scattered* in a CLIL setting influence the intercultural competencies of students. Based on a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the activity booklets completed by secondary school students during several lessons taught by an English and geography teacher, it can be concluded that the combination, and specifically the visual and cultural aspects, have a considerable positive influence in developing or improving elements of students' intercultural competences.

7.1 Reflection of the procedure

While the constraints outlined in Chapter 5.3 limit the generalization of the results, this approach offers fresh perspectives on utilizing a graphic memoir depicting a refugee experience within a CLIL context to develop intercultural competencies in students. The initial findings warrant further exploration of this research on a larger scale.

The CLIL method was chosen so students could acquire background knowledge on the geographical aspects of migration and better understand the actions and choices of the characters in the graphic memoir. This choice seemed good as students proved they gained much new knowledge on Somalia's history and climate and general reasons for migration through the tasks. Unfortunately, how the students used this knowledge in their assessment and evaluation of situations in the novel did not become explicit. They possibly used the geographical aspects to reach their conclusions and write their responses, but they did not make them explicit. It would make sense to prompt students to justify their responses in greater detail when repeating this experiment.

The qualitative analysis was chosen to allow students to show what they learned and express their opinions and views. This choice proved to be fitting and led to fruitful answers. However, this openness in the tasks also led to diverse answers that were sometimes difficult to compare. One reason for this might be that not all students understood the question or task in the same or the correct way. Therefore, it would be helpful to either have the lessons taught by the researcher so that they can explain the tasks abundantly clearly or to make the tasks more easily understandable in a future execution.

7.2 Consequences for teaching and outlook

Based on the conclusions expressed in the previous chapters, using graphic memoirs on refugee experiences in a CLIL context is an excellent way to develop IC. Focus should be put on the visuals and cultural elements in the novel, as these were the aspects that showed the most significant impact on the improvement of the students' intercultural competence in this study. Nevertheless, the geographical and text-based elements should not be left out and could even be fostered more to increase the students' use of them.

This project aimed to introduce a fresh outlook, addressing an overlooked area of research related to utilizing authentic graphic memoirs and geographic knowledge to foster intercultural competence within the ELT classroom. With the lesson plan, the qualitative analysis of the activity booklet, and the quantitative analysis of the student's self-assessment, this was achieved and showed that specifically, the visual and cultural aspects of the memoir aided students in developing and improving their intercultural competence.

8 Index of used aids and acknowledgments

I thank Nikola Mayer and Nicole Frey Büchel for their review of sections of my thesis and their insightful feedback during our meetings. Their valuable opinions also contributed to refining the title and structure of the thesis.

A special thanks goes out to Joy Bond for implementing my lesson plan in her class and providing me with the booklets completed by her students. These booklets served as the basis for my subsequent analysis.

I thank my cousin, Marina, for her proofreading of my thesis. Her feedback provided valuable insights, guiding me in enhancing the precision and overall revision of the content.

Additionally, I acknowledge the utilization of ChatGPT in this thesis to explain the difference between global and intercultural competence. Furthermore, in combination with the Grammarly app, ChatGPT played a role in the linguistic revision of my text.

9 Bibliography

- Adobe. n.d. *Serifenschriften und serifenlose Schriften erklärt* | Adobe. Accessed November 1, 2023.
<https://www.adobe.com/de/creativecloud/design/discover/serif-vs-sans-serif.html#:~:text=%E2%80%9ESerifen%20machen%20kleiner%20gedruckte%20Texte,%E2%80%9C>.
- Anderson, Porter. 2023. *Germany: 'IGLU' Shows School Reading Skills Lagging*. May 25. Accessed August 08, 2023.
<https://publishingperspectives.com/2023/05/germany-iglu-shows-primary-school-reading-skills-lagging/>.
- Bakar, Abu Yazid Abu, Dayang Nurfaezah Abang Ahmad, and Melor Md Yunus. 2020. "STUDENTS' ACCEPTANCE TO USING GRAPHIC NOVELS IN LEARNING LITERATURE (L2): A MALAYSIAN CASE STUDY." *Social Sciences, Humanities and Education Journal* 1 (2): 43-51.
- Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich. 2017. March 13. Accessed October 04, 2023. <https://zh.lehrplan.ch/>.
- Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich. 2017. *Lehrplan Volksschule Englisch*. March 13. Accessed October 10, 2023.
<https://zh.lehrplan.ch/index.php?code=a|1|21|2|1|2>.
- Bildungsdirektion des Kantons Zürich. 2017. "Lehrplan Volksschule Sprachen." *Lehrplan Volksschule Kanton Zürich*. March 13. Accessed August 7, 2023.
https://zh.lehrplan.ch/container/ZH_DE_Fachbereich_SPR.pdf.
- Bon, Saban. 2022. "Developing Cambodian secondary school students' intercultural competence: Strategies and challenges." *Issues in Educational Research* 32 (3): 887-905.
<http://www.iier.org.au/iier32/bon.pdf>.
- Burmark, Lynell. 2008. "Visual Literacy: What You Get is What You See." Chap. 1 in *Teaching Visual Literacy: Using Comic Books, Graphic Novels, Anime, Cartoons, and More to Develop Comprehension and Thinking Skills*, edited by Nancy Frey and Douglas Fisher, 5-26. Thousand Oaks, California: Corwin Press.
- Burwitz-Melzer, Eva. 2001. "Teaching Intercultural Communicative Competence through Literature." In *Developing Intercultural Competence in Practice*, edited by Michael Byram, Adam Nichols and David Stevens, 29-42. Bristol, Blue Ridge Summit: Multilingual Matters.
- Byram, Michael. 1997. *Teaching and Assessing Intercultural Communicative Competence*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters LTD.

- Byram, Michael. 2008. *From Foreign Language Education to Education for Intercultural Citizenship: Essays and Reflections*. Bristol, Blue Ridge Summit: Multilingual Matters. doi:doi.org/10.21832/9781847690807.
- Byram, Michael. 2021. *Teaching and Assessing Intercultural Communicative Competence: Revisited*. 2. Bristol, Blue Ridge Summit: Multilingual Matters. doi:doi.org/10.21832/BYRAM0244.
- Cakir, Ismail. 2006. "Developing Cultural Awareness In Foreign Language Teaching." *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education* 7 (3): 154-161.
- Cary, Stephen. 2004. *Going graphic: comics at work in the multilingual classroom*. Portsmouth: Heinemann.
- Chiappini, Riccardo. 2021. "Using literature with children." *English Teaching Professional* (134): 24-27.
- Daskalovska, Nina, and Violeta Dimova. 2012. "Why should literature be used in the language classroom?" *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 46: 1182-1186.
- Deardorff, Darla K. 2011. "Assessing intercultural competence." *New Directions for Institutional Research* 2011 (149): 65-79. doi:doi.org/10.1002/ir.381.
- Deardorff, Darla K. 2020. "Defining, Developing and Assessing Intercultural Competence." In *The Cambridge Handbook of Intercultural Communication*, edited by Guido Rings and Sebastian Rasinger, 493-503. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/9781108555067.
- Deardorff, Darla K. 2006. "Identification and Assessment of Intercultural Competence as a Student Outcome of Internationalization." *Journal of Studies in International Education* 10 (3): 241-266. doi:10.1177/102831530628700.
- Deardorff, Darla K., and William Hunter. 2006. "Educating Global-Ready Graduates." *International Educator* 15 (3): 72-83.
- Eder, Barbara. 2016. "Graphic Novels." In *Comics and Graphic Novels*, edited by Julia Abel and Christian Klein, 156-168. Stuttgart: J.B. Metzler. doi:10.1007/978-3-476-05443-2_8.
- Eisenmann, Maria. 2022. "Die Förderung visueller Kompetenz durch Comics." In *Was kann der Comic für den Unterricht leisten? Fachdidaktische Perspektiven auf ein subversives Erzählmedium*, edited by Heinrich Ammerer and Markus Oppolzer, 57-75. Münster: Waxmann.
- Eisner, Will. 1985. *Comics and sequential art: Principles and practice of the world's most popular art form*. Cincinnati: North Light Books.
- European Commission. 2022. *Statistics on migration to Europe*. October 27.

Accessed April 12, 2023. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life/statistics-migration-europe_en.

- Frank, Jerrold. 2013. "Raising Cultrual Awareness in the English Language Classroom." *English Teaching Forum* 2-11.
- Freitag-Hild, Britta. 2022. "Young Adult Literature and critical literacy - politische Bildung im fremdsprachlichen Literaturunterricht." Edited by Lutz Küster, Birgit Schädlich, Karen Schramm and Britta Viebrock. *Fremdsprachen Lehren und Lernen* (Narr Francke Attempto Verlag) 51 (1): 107-120.
- Fresacher, Candy. 2017. "Colors in images: developing color vocabulary and meanings in the EFL classroom." In *The Image in English Language Teaching*, edited by Kieran Donaghy and Daniel Xerri, 71-78. Malta: ELT Council.
- Gavigan, Karen W., and Mindy Tomasevich. 2011. *Connecting Comics to Curriculum: strategies for Grades 6-12*. Santa Barbara: Libraries Unlimited.
- Gillenwater, Cary. 2009. "Lost literacy: How graphic novels can recover visual literacy in the literacy classroom." *Afterimage* 37 (2): 33-36.
- Grimm, Nancy, Michael Meyer, and Laurenz Volkmann. 2015. *Teaching English*. Tübingen: Narr Francke Attempto Verlag GmbH + Co. KG.
- Grünewald, Dietrich. 2022. "Comics lesen lernen." In *Was kann der Comic für den Unterricht leisten?- Fachdidaktische Perspektiven auf ein subversives Erzählmedium*, edited by Heinrich Ammerer and Markus Oppolzer, 17-42. Münster and New York: Waxmann.
- Gultom, Solina Eva, Adelle Frans, and Esperanza Cellay. 2022. "Adapting the Graphic Novel to Improve Speaking Fluency for EFL Learners." *Al-Hijr: Journal of Adulearn World* 1 (1): 46-54.
- Habegger-Conti, Jena. 2021. "'Where am I in the text?' Standing with Refugees in Graphic Narratives." *Children's Literature in English Language Education* 52-66.
- Heinrich Schoch, Yvonne, Michael Hürlimann, Monika Reuschenbach, and Michael Studer. 2019a. *Weltsicht: Arbeitsheft 2*. Zürich: Lehrmittelverlag Zürich.
- Heinrich Schoch, Yvonne, Michael Hürlimann, Monika Reuschenbach, and Michael Studer. 2019b. *Weltsicht: Themenbuch 2*. Zürich: Lehrmittelverlag Zürich.
- Hoff, Hild Elisabeth. 2020. "The Evolution of Intercultural Communicative Competence: Conceptualisations, Critiques and Consequences for 21st

- Century Classroom Practice." *Intercultural Communication Education* 3 (2): 55-74. doi:doi.org/10.29140/ice.v3n2.264.
- Hoffmann, Jeanette, and Lynn Mastellotto. 2023. "Storytelling in multilingual and intercultural contexts - An Introduction." *Zeitschrift für Interkulturellen Fremdsprachenunterricht* 28 (1): 19-34. doi:10.48694/zif.3615.
- IEA PIRLS. 2023. *PIRLS 2021*. June 26. Accessed August 08, 2023. <https://pirls2021.org/>.
- Jamieson, Victoria. n.d. *About Me*. Accessed November 1, 2023. <https://www.victoriajamieson.com/about-me/>.
- Kelly, Lois. 2013. "Why use a cross-curricular approach to teaching and learning?" In *Enhancing Primary Science: Developing Effective Cross-Curricular Links*, edited by Lois Kelly and Di Stead, 1-11. New York: Open University Press.
- Kennedy, Uthumporn, and Sumalee Chinokul. 2020. "Effect of the Scaffolded Reading Experience using a Graphic Novel on the English Reading Comprehension and Reading Motivation of Thai EFL students." *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network Journal* 13 (2): 158-175.
- Khatib, Mohammad, Saeed Rezaei, and Ali Derakhshan. 2011. "Literature in EFL/ESL Classroom." *English Language Teaching* 4 (1): 201-208.
- Kuckartz, Udo, and Stefan Rädiker. 2022. *Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse. Methoden, Praxis, Computerunterstützung*. 5. Beltz Juventa.
- Lewis, Ioan M. 2023. *History of Somalia*. October 27. Accessed November 29, 2023. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/history-of-Somalia>.
- Lewis, Samantha. 2017. "Using graphic novels and comics with ELT learners." Chap. 16 in *The Image in English Language Teaching*, edited by Kieran Donaghy and Daniel Xerri, 165-178. Malta: ELT Council.
- Llull, Josué. 2014. "Comics and CLIL: Producing quality output in social sciences with Hergé's The Adventures of Tintin." *Latin American Journal of Content and Language Integrated Learning* 7 (1): 40-65. doi:10.5294/laclil.2014.7.1.3 eISSN 2322-9721.
- Mayer, Nikola. 2022. "Breaking down barriers - Englische Lektüre in einfacher Sprache." Edited by Lutz Küster, Birgit Schädlich, Karen Schramm and Britta Viebrock. *FLUL: Fremdsprachen Lehren und Lernen* (Narr Francke Attempto Verlag) 51 (1): 90-106.
- McCloud, Scott. 1993. *Understanding Comics: The invisible art*. New York: HarperCollins Publishers.

- Meltzer, Rachel. 2022. *Memoir vs. Autobiography: What's the Difference?* June 7. Accessed April 14, 2023. <https://www.grammarly.com/blog/memoir-vs-autobiography/>.
- Mohamed, Omar, and Victoria Jamieson. 2020. *When Stars Are Scattered*. Penguin Group USA.
- Ms. Magazine. n.d. *Iman Geddy, Author at Ms. Magazine*. Zugriff am 1. November 2023. <https://msmagazine.com/author/igeddy/>.
- National Book Foundation. 2020. *Omar Mohamed*. October 5. Accessed November 1, 2023. <https://www.nationalbook.org/people/omar-mohamed/>.
- Nodelman, Perry. 2012. "Picture Book Guy Looks at Comics: Structural Differences in Two Kinds of Visual Narrative." *Children's Literature Association Quarterly* (Johns Hopkins University Press) 37 (4): 436-444. doi:10.1353/chq.2012.0049.
- Ntarangwi, Mwenda, Kenneth Ingham, and Simeon Hongo Ominde. 2023. *Kenya*. October 31. Accessed November 1, 2023. <https://www.britannica.com/place/Kenya>.
- Nugent, Kristen, and Theresa Catalano. 2015. "Critical cultural awareness in the foreign language classroom." *The NECTFL Review* 75 15-30.
- Nugent, Kristen, and Theresa Catalano. 2015. "Critical cultural awareness in the foreign language classroom." *The NECTFL Review* 75: 15-30.
- Olagbaju, Oladotun Opeoluwa. 2020. "Literature-in-English as a Tool for Fostering Intercultural Communicative Competence in Multicultural Classrooms in Nigeria." *Konfrontasi Journal: Culture, Economy, and Social Changes* 7 (1): 40-49. doi:10.33258/konfrontasi2.v7i1.95.
- Oziewicz, Marek. 2018. "The graphic novel: Brian Selznick's THE INVENTION OF HUGO CABRET, WONDERSTRUCK and THE MARVELS." In *Using Literature in English Language Education: Challenging Reading for 8-18 Year Olds*, edited by Janice Bland. London: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Penguin School, and Library Marketing. 2019. "When Stars Are Scattered." *Penguin Classroom*. Accessed April 12, 2023. <https://www.penguinclassroom.com/books/when-stars-are-scattered/>.
- Prusse, Michael. 2022. "Bringing "the world into the classroom": Children's and young adult literature in English language teaching." *ETAS Journal* 39 (1): 56-58.
- Reitbauer, Margit, Ulla Fürstenberg, Petra Kletzenbauer, and Karoline Marko. 2018. "Towards a Cognitive-Linguistic Turn in CLIL: Unfolding Integration."

LACLIL 11 (1): 87-107. doi:10.5294/LACLIL.2018.11.1.5.

Rouse, Brad. 2021. *Graphic Novels Continue to Push Boundaries*. September 23. <https://www.libraryjournal.com/story/graphic-novels-continue-to-push-boundaries-lj210923>.

Schwarz, Gretchen. 2006. "Expanding Literacies through Graphic Novels." *The English Journal* (National Council of Teachers of English) 95 (6): 58-64. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/30046629>.

Shukla, Sheobhushan, and Anu Shukla. 2006. *Migrant Voices in Literatures in English*. New Delhi: Sarup & Sons.

SLJ Staff. 2020. "SLJ's Reviews of the 2020 National Book Award Finalists." *School Library Journal*. <https://www.slj.com/story/slj-reviews-2020-national-book-award-finalists>.

Thaler, Engelbert. 2016. *Teaching English Literature*. 2. Schöningh: Brill.

UNHCR. 2023. *Refugee Data Finder*. June 14. Accessed July 31, 2023. <https://www.unhcr.org/refugee-statistics/>.

Wang, Xiuqing, and Kelly Donovan. 2020. "Using Identity to Introduce ICC Skills in the EFL Classroom." *English Teaching Forum* 58 (4): 42-48.

Xerri Hili, Charlene, and Heathcliff Schembri. 2022. "Cross-Curricular Teaching Within the Learning Outcomes Framework: The Experiences of Primary Teachers in Two State Schools in Malta." *Malta Journal of Education* 3 (2): 231-258.

Zandian, Samaneh. 2015. "Migrant literature and teaching English as an international language in Iran." In *English language teaching in the Islamic Republic of Iran: Innovations, trends and challenges*, edited by Chris Kennedy, 113-122. London: British Council.

Zürich, Bildungsdirektion des Kantons. 2017. *Strukturelle und inhaltliche Hinweise zu den Sprachen*. March 13. Accessed October 10, 2023. <https://zh.lehrplan.ch/index.php?code=e|1|4>.

10 Appendix

A) Lesson plan

B) Code book Excel

C) Answers from the students' activity booklets

Appendix A: Lesson plan

Lesson	Topic	Aims and goals	Learning process/learning arrangements/activities	Material other than the booklet	GN excerpt pg.
1 & 2	Introduction to novel and topic	<p>I can name two reasons for fleeing and understand that it is usually a combination of reasons that cause a person to flee.</p> <p>I can explain the difference between refugees and internally displaced persons.</p> <p>I can justify my opinion about a statement.</p>	<p>10' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anticipating what the novel could be about with the cover image and the title (Booklet pg. 2, ex. a) in class. <p>10' Pre-reading reflection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Statements for individual stance to judge cultural competence (Booklet pg. 1, ex. b and c). Faster students: Compare their answers in pairs <p>20' Refugees in media:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Image description of a refugee boat. (Booklet pg. 2, ex. d) Interpretation of image in combination with own feelings. (Booklet pg. 2, ex. e and f) Faster students: try to think of other places or situations where they have seen images like the one in the booklet. 		Cover

			<p>15' Fleeing places in Africa:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Table for different countries in Africa using <i>Weltsicht</i>. (Booklet pg. 2, ex. g) • Difference between refugees and internally displaced persons. (Booklet pg. 3, ex. h and i) <p>5' Graphic novels in detail:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different parts of a graphic novel page (Booklet pg. 4, ex. j) • Faster students: discuss their previous knowledge of and experiences with graphic novels. <p>15' Culture journal entries 1 and 2.</p> <p>5' What I learned in today's lesson.</p>		
3	Framing the novel and the background	<p>I can describe what a refugee camp may look like.</p> <p>I can briefly describe the political situation which caused many people to flee from Somalia.</p> <p>I can name key points in the plot of <i>When Stars Are Scattered</i>.</p>	<p>5' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write the following questions on the board: What is a refugee camp? Why do people go to refugee camps? What do you know about refugee camps? • Allow the students 2-3 minutes to discuss the questions in pairs or small groups. • Then, invite them to share their responses with the class. 		-

			<p>15' Localizing and characterizing Dadaab camp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locating Somalia, Kenya, and Dadaab on a map (Booklet pg. 5, ex. a and b) • Comparing the drawings of Dadaab to actual pictures of the camp (Booklet pg. 6, ex. c). • Climate in Kenya (Booklet pg. 6, ex. d). <p>15' Acquiring knowledge through texts about the novel and the real-life political situation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read two texts and highlight keywords (Booklet pg. 6, ex. e). • Students meet, discuss, and summarize the texts (Booklet pg. 7, ex. f). <p>10' Culture journal entry 3 and What I learned in today's lesson.</p>		
4	Life in the refugee camp Dadaab	I can use a video and a graphic novel to explain life in a refugee camp.	<p>10' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have students think of 10 items that fit the criteria: Things to do to pass the time. • Link what they do to pass the time and what life is like in the refugee camp Dadaab for Omar. 		<p>Intro</p> <p>Ch. 1</p> <p>60-64</p> <p>67</p> <p>0</p>

			<p>25' Life in the refugee camp:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch a video of Ifo Town to gather information on Dadaab's town center (Booklet pg. 9, ex. a). • Analyze Omar's life using the graphic novel (Booklet pg. 9, ex. a) • Use the acquired knowledge to describe life in a refugee camp (Booklet pg. 9, ex. b). • Faster students: Find more information about Ifo Town on the internet and use this to make your description in b) more detailed. <p>10' Culture journal entry 4.</p> <p>5' What I learned in today's lesson.</p>	
5	Identity wheel	I can understand that aspects of a person's identity, such as age, sex, social class, and place of residence, affect how people speak and behave.	<p>10' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ask the class to think of one thing they can do that nobody else can do. For example, a student could ask the class, can you count to ten in Chinese? • Students ask the question, and whoever can't do it sits down. This way, it is clear to see who has the same skills. 	Intro Ch. 1 Pg. 42-2

			<p>15' Describing one's own as well as Omar's identity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating your identity wheel (Booklet pg. 10, ex. a and b). • Creating an identity wheel for Omar (Booklet pg. 10, ex. c). <p>10' Discussing identities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss your identity wheel and Omar's wheel with partners with the form Inner and Outer Circle (Booklet pg. 10-11, ex. d). <p>10' Culture journal entry 5 and what I learned in today's lesson.</p>		
6	Framing and positioning	<p>I can explain the effect, where the reader is looking from in a panel, can have on the reader.</p> <p>E: I can use the terms <i>framing</i> and <i>positioning</i> to explain how an author can make a reader feel more like a part of the story.</p>	<p>10' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Picture prompt with the first image of the graphic novel <i>When Stars Are Scattered</i> (in Booklet pg. 13). • Give students time to study the image and then ask them what they see. Focus on details, actions, and what the people in the picture might be feeling. • Introduce the terms <i>framing</i> and <i>perspective</i> using the first image of the graphic novel. <p>10' Comparing points of view:</p>		First image

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparing the cover image of <i>Illegal</i> and the first image in <i>When Stars Are Scattered</i> (Booklet pg. 13, ex. a). • Analyzing the image when Omar gets the letter (Booklet pg. 14, ex. b). <p>10' Linking points of view with emotions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differences in how the reader is involved and how it makes us feel (Booklet pg. 14, ex. c). <p>10' Culture journal entry 6. 5' What I learned in today's lesson.</p>		
7	Cultural observations	I can understand why people act the way they do in certain situations.	<p>10' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the website on the right to add 4 topics to the wheel: clothing, food, hobbies, and living. • Put the students into groups of 4, they number themselves from 1-4. • Spin the wheel to choose the first topic. All the number one must talk about that topic for one minute without stopping; if they stop or have a long pause, they've lost the challenge. • Make the challenge more difficult by having students talk for 2 minutes instead. 	https://edutools.ch/	Pg. 19-21, 26, 51, 63, 68, 99, 164-165, 147-151

			<p>20' Understanding why people act the way they do in certain situations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyzing how people in the novel act and look (Booklet pg. 15, ex. a). Reflecting on one's practices (Booklet pg. 15, ex. b). Comparing cultural observations in the novel with one's own culture by finding similarities (Booklet pg. 15, ex. c). Faster students: draw a Venn diagram for the cultural observations about the characters in the novel and themselves. <p>10' Culture journal entry 7.</p> <p>5' What I learned in today's lesson.</p>		
8	Emotions	<p>I can describe characters' emotions using colors, text, and facial expressions in a graphic novel.</p> <p>I can understand the meaning of the "Poem of Stars."</p>	<p>5' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Play the video on the right, which displays very strong emotions. Have students discuss the emotions shown and how they are displayed. <p>15' Defining emotions based on colors, text, and facial expressions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describing emotions (Booklet pg. 16, ex. a, b, and c) 	<p>https://youtu.be/nEUzQ7yL9A0</p>	<p>Ch. 13, 14, and 16</p> <p>Pg. 120</p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflecting on how we can deduct these emotions (Booklet pg. 16, ex. c) • Linking emotions and colors and comparing the effect (Booklet pg. 16, ex. d). <p>15' Meaning of the "Poem of Stars"</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading the poem (Booklet pg. 17, ex. a). • Discuss the poem's meaning in pairs (Booklet pg. 17, ex. f). • Faster students: write their poem (Booklet pg. 18, ex. j). <p>10' Culture journal entry 8 and what I learned in today's lesson.</p>		
9	Conclusion of the novel	I am curious about the target culture and have empathy toward its people.	<p>10' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show students the video on the right. • In pairs, students collect what they know about life in the United States. <p>10' Comparing life in the refugee camp to life in the United States:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading the last chapter of the GN (Booklet pg. 19, ex. a). • Comparing how life would be different for Omar in the US compared to the refugee camp (Booklet pg. 19, ex. b). 	https://youtube.com/shorts/wh3bun5WyOM?feature=share	Pg. 251-257

			<p>10' Matchbox diary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students summarize Omar's life by thinking of a matchbox diary for him (Booklet pg. 20, ex. d) • Faster students: create the actual matchbox diary. <p>10' "No one chooses to become a refugee":</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explaining the powerful sentence (Booklet pg. 19, ex. c). <p>5' What I learned in today's lesson.</p>		
10 (Half a lesson)	Evaluation		<p>5' Warm-up:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students go through the booklet and read what they wrote in the boxes "What I learned today" at the end of each lesson. <p>10' post-reading reflection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statements for individual stance to judge cultural competence (Booklet pg. 21, ex. a, b). • Faster students: Compare their answers in pairs. • Comparing pre- and post-reading reflections (Booklet pg. 21, ex. c). <p>10' Evaluation of graphic novel:</p>		

			<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Opinion on the GN (Booklet pg. 21, ex. d, e).• Evaluation of how the novel helped them achieve the goals (Booklet pg. 21, ex. f). <p>Hand in the booklet, including the culture journal.</p>		
--	--	--	---	--	--

Appendix B: Code book Excel

Name	Coding rule	Anchorexample
1. Visual aspects		
1.1 colors	Student answers referring to the interpretation of colors used.	"Red: sad and angry, red mostly represents anger so it's used to show Omar's anger. White: in my opinion it represents calmness or even sadness."
1.2 facial expressions	Student answers referring to the interpretation of facial expressions drawn.	"I could tell that he was happy because he was smiling."
1.3 new knowledge	Student answers referring to new knowledge on the refugee camp they gained based on visuals in the novel.	"If they want to play soccer they have to make a ball out of trash bags."
1.4 interpretations	Student answers referring to interpretations they made based on visuals in the novel.	"I think this book is about two friends that live in Africa. In the picture of this book I can see trees from Africa"
2. Text-based aspects		
2.1 emotions and feelings	Student answers referring to emotions and feelings they understood based on text in the novel.	"Sad, because of his word choice"
2.2 events	Student answers referring to events they understood based on text in the novel.	"Celebrate the end of Ramadan with Eid-Al Fitr, a big holiday."
2.4 new knowledge	Student answers referring to new knowledge they gained on refugee camps based on text in the novel.	"In the first 10 days they have a lot of food, but the last 5 days they don't have enough food and all the people are very angry."
3. Geographical aspects		
3.1 climate	Student answers referring to the climate in the graphic novel.	"Kenya looks very dry and sunny. It looks extremely hot there."
3.2 consequences of climate on people	Student answers referring to the consequences the climate has on the people in the graphic novel.	"Dress: because it's hot."
3.3 comparing the climate of the novel to own climate	Student answers referring to a comparison between the climate in Kenya and the climate in Switzerland.	"A difference would be the climate because in Kenya it's much dryer and hotter than in Switzerland."
3.4 reasons for fleeing	Student answers referring to reasons why people flee from their homelands.	"1. Resource crisis, such as shortage of food and water. 2. War reasons"
4. Cultural aspects of the graphic novel		
4.1 comparing to own life	Student answers referring to a similarity of aspects of life in a refugee camp and aspects of their own lives.	"We both are students and learn a language"
4.2 contrasting to own life	Student answers referring to differences between life in a refugee camp and aspects of their own lives.	"They also have a school but it's not the same like we have. They don't have the equipment like us."
4.3 curiosity	Student answers showing that they are curious about other cultures.	I agree with the statement "I am curious about other cultures."
4.4 knowledge on cultural practices	Student answers referring to knowledge they gained of cultural practices in Somali culture.	"I think all of the women have headscarves on. They celebrate Ramadan and Eid Al-Fitr."
4.5 interpretation of events	Student answers explaining and interpreting religion in Somali culture.	"They are Muslim and religion is very important to them. They all got together for praying and celebrating."

Appendix C: Answers from the students' activity booklets

Task 1a (introduction)

- I think it is about poor children in Afrika because they don't wear shoes and the background is looking like Afrika.
- I think this book is about two friends that live in Africa. In the picture of this book I can see trees from Africa. I can also see like small houses.
- I think it is about two Afrikan boys who want to explore the world, but their mother stops them.
- Maybe about the relationship between 2 brothers or friends, or a refugee camp. There is a tree in the title which is only in Afrika. And tents in the background that's how I knew it was a camp.
- Is a sad book with many stars. This is a book that plays in Africa. I mean is a story of two brothers.
- I think that this book is about two kids from Africa, because there are some trees, that I have only seen in Africa, and it looks like, as if there's also a small village. The boys aren't wearing any shoes and are looking at the stars.
- It could be about dreams and a camp because of the stars and the tents. I think it's about two African boys. Trees in the background in Africa because of the three tents in the back. In the front are boys without shoes.
- I think this boys are from Africa, because they have no shoes on. Sky full of stars, two boys, houses, ...
- The peoples live poor and they have to make an adventure to achieve/get something very important.
- I think these two African boys have a dream. For example they want to begin a new life in an European country.
- I think the story plays in Africa and the two boys are maybe poor because they wear no shoes. I think the stars are scattered means they fell from the sky.
- It could be about children that are surviving in Africa. There are some tents and two trees also children are without any shoes. That means that they live in those tents, and they are poor.
- It's about two brothers that live in a poor village in Africa. They try to survive together. Poor village / stars in a blue-red sky / two young boys / two trees.
- I think this story is about two brothers. They live in a small poor camp and they try to survive. On the cover of the book you can see two boys walking in front of a camp with tents.
- It's about two brothers that are poor. We see that the trees are like trees out of Africa. So I guess it plays in Africa. I think the genre is: tragedy or adventure.

- I think this book is about hopes and dreams of a poor boy. There is an evening sky filled with stars. There are two boys walking bare foot behind them is a village and two African looking trees.
- I think that the book about hopes and dreams. I'm sure that it plays in Africa, judging by the trees in the background. The book could also be about war and fleeing.
- It might be about 2 brothers who are poor. Or about some kids locked up in a camp (even though they look really happy) who are trying to escape.
- Maybe their life wasn't so good and later something changed. They are maybe brothers and good friends. He's in Africa I think.

Task 1d

- I see many people in boat. They are looking tired. They are in warm clothes.
- I can see people on a boat fleeing to reach a better country where no war is going on.
- Many mostly black people try to flee. They don't have much space in that small boat and still so many are in the boat. They look exhausted.
- The boat looks old and not safe. There are most likely too many people in this boat. Everyone is wearing jackets.
- The person wants a better home and a new life in another country with other people.
- As you can see the boat is full with refugees. You can barely find an empty place to stand or sit down. The boat itself isn't in the best condition and very old. It's dark outside, so it's probably night.
- On this picture are so many refugees on the boat fleeing from their country. I think it's in the night and cold because of their clothes. The boat they are in looks very old.
- In the picture I can see a blue boat with white stripes. Of this boat I can see many people. The blue boat floats on the water. All of these people are wearing a jacket.
- It is a small boat with a lot of people and it's really dangerous. If someone finds them they probably get sent back to their country.
- There are a lot of people on a not great looking boat. They are not happy. They are in the middle of nowhere.
- There are many people in a boat trying to escape at night. The boat is very old and rusty. It's maybe a little bit scary.
- There are many refugees on that old boat. They are trying to flee in another country. They are wearing some warm clothes it seems. It was cold.
- The people on the boat are trying to leave their country with a cheap, old and overloaded boat. It's not a safe option but the cheapest. They take it because they may have lost their homes and got poor for whatever reason.

- On this picture you can see a boat with a lot of people in it. They are trying to escape a country. There isn't much space on the boat, because it's full of people.
- I can see a small boat in the water. The boat is cramped full with people. The boat is painted blue with a white stripe.
- There are very many people so they're all poor and want a better life. The boat doesn't look that good, what leads us to the fact that the helpers are also poor. It is going to be a hard journey to another country. It depends on which country you are in (war).
- There are a lot of people on the boat. It seems to be night since the sky is dark. Almost everyone is wearing the same coat.
- The people look scared. They are scared that the boat will sink since they know they are too many. They are probably overwhelmed and are obviously desperate to find a better home.

Task 1e

- I would be scared. I can swim but it's dark and there are so many people that anything can happen.
- Afraid, hopeful, exhausted, eventful
- Sad, bad, poor, unhappy, negative, overfilled
- Afraid, worried, sad, happy, scared
- I would be afraid about that boat tour and where it will go.
- I am going to feel kind of scared and happy.
- Scared, lost, tired, bedrängt
- I would be very scared because I heard a lot of stories where refugees died, and I would be extra scared because of the horrible looking boat.
- I would feel scared because if someone finds me I probably would be sent back to the country I fled from.
- I think I would be afraid.
- I think I would feel sad and scared, because there are so many people.
- I would somehow feel sad to leave my country, but also somehow happy to escape from war and hopefully start my life in another country from the start.
- I feel happy for a new life and sad because I have to go from my old life. I am scared because the sea is dangerous.
- Sad, cold, scared, emotional
- I would feel broken, sad, jealous that others have better lives and probably emotional and tired.
- Sad, tired, emotional, happy that I survived, scared
- Scared, sad

Task 2c (framing the novel and background)

- The tents look the same. It looks like a small city.
- Similar - the houses and how they are in rows. Different - not in all places there are plants and not always little plots.
- It's a similar style of camp (rows of tents) but it has more green to it.
- The houses in the book look very similar to the ones in real life. The way that there are roads is similar. In the picture the huts are in a square patch together, but not in real life.
- Dadaab looks much smaller in the drawing. The houses in the drawing look very similar to the pictures. There are more trees in the drawing.
- There are many little huts and long ways through the camp. On the picture it looks like there are nearly no plants but on the drawing, there are a lot. The camp looks smaller on the drawing.
- Tents look like same. There are trees on the booth picture. On the real pictures tents are not scattered.
- The houses are in all the pictures hemisphere. In the real picture it's bigger than in the drawing.
- The huts are looking similar. The streets are the same. The IFO camp looks prolific.
- The houses look very same and on both pictures it don't have a lot of green. But in real life the houses are not really old and it's a lot bigger than I thought.
- Dadaab is so big. It has so much tents/huts. Many people can live in this refugee camp.
- On the picture are trees but on the original picture are many less trees. The huts are the same. The streets between the huts are on both pictures. On the real one are more huts in one quarter.
- The differences are that at the drawing can't be seen military people guarding the post and in the picture there aren't many trees seen. The tents look on the drawing and picture very similar and you also can see different blocks of small tent groups.
- Of all pictures has a tent. Of the pictures has people. From when stars are scattered Dadaab is smaller than the picture. Picture 1 (drawing) has animal on picture 2/3 not.
- The tents in all photos are sort of round. In all photos there is sand on the ground. In the photo from the book it looks like there is more nature.
- In both pictures the tents are round. The streets look almost the same. There are more people in the real pictures. There are way more plants in the drawing.
- The similarities are this houses and the desert. I think the differences are the trees (in picture more).

- At the drawing is no military but on the picture there is. The picture looks more modern than the drawing.

Task 2d

- Sunny and dry because the floor is made from sand and there isn't many grass.
- Kenya looks very dry and sunny. It looks extremely hot there.
- In Kenya the climate is hot and tropical, but it's mostly pleasant.
- It looks very dry. I can tell because the ground looks sandy. It also looks hot. I can tell because Kenya is close to the equator.
- I think the climate in Kenya is very sunny, dry and hot, because the people in the picture are wearing airy clothes and the plants look very dry.
- Hot, sunny, tropical, humid. Kenya is close to the equator so it's located in the tropical zone of the earth.
- I think it's dry and hot there, and cold in the night.
- It's dry but not too hot and sometimes it rains at night the temperature sinks to 10°.
- Dry: everything looks yellow like in a desert. Hot: on every picture, it is very sunny.
- The climate in Kenya is special: the sun nearly shines the whole day and the air humidity is very so it doesn't rain very much.
- Hot, dry, very sunny. The floor is very dry and not many plants can.
- Hot on the day and cold in the night, it's very dry, it's very sunny.
- The climate in Kenya is very dry and hot. It seems like it doesn't rain often there. By looking at the picture Kenya looks more like a big desert.
- Tropical because it is in the tropics. Sunny because it has hot season.
- I think it looks quite hot because the camp looks like kinda in the middle of a desert. But it can't be too hot, because there are some trees.
- It looks dry and moist because of the desert. And also clima changing. Because they cover themselves up during the day because of the sun and have a thick tent for the cold night.
- There is hot.
- It is very hot there because there is much sun and it's very dry and sometimes windy.

Task 3b (life in the refugee camp Dadaab)

- They have it quite hard. It's not easy they always hope for the better but it just never really happens. They hunger, suffer and a lot of people die. They don't get enough food. They are all waiting for something better.
- Life in a refugee camp always feels like waiting, waiting for food, water, help. A lot of people seem to be having nightmares about their past. I

think living there would be a huge adjustment. I think that it would be difficult at some times especially resource wise. Being there without a parent must be even harder.

- It seems that the people of Dadaab don't have many resources (wood, vegetables, medicine), which can alter the quality of life. I also noticed that there is not enough food for them, there are days where there is nothing. That can lead to hunger and weakness. It also seems like there is a lot of sadness in the camp. That can be bad because other people will also get sad. It's probably bad that they have no proper housing.
- Life isn't good, you get food only every 15 days and you're close to starving on the last 5 days. They don't have much money (poor) and their life is kind of like a long staircase, you have to keep going even if your powerless and you know there isn't an end near (hopeless).
- The people in refugee camps are very poor. They just have a small amount of food to survive. They have to wait in line for a very long time to get water. Some people are waiting since 7 years to move to America. If the kids go to school, they have to walk. A lot of people get sick because they don't have enough food, water, and sleep. The children can't concentrate in school, because of all these conditions.
- They live poor and have just the amount of food and water to survive. They all wait on a better future. The United Nations can do it and is hope for the refugees. It's a luxury when they have enough food for the 15 days, have enough water to drink, wash and cook. And have friends to enjoy some moments of the day.
- There isn't that much food and water, so they are hungry. They lay on hard floor. They have no shoes. They are always waiting.
- In the refugee camp you have to wait long times to get food or water. When you're in a refugee camp it's very stressful. It's a bit frustrating there and maybe you lost your parents and you're lonely. In the camp it's sandy and everywhere is sand and it's annoying to have all the sand on the food or inside the house.
- Sleep: you see there are many people with nightmares -> because of war, etc. Food: every 15 days you get a ration. In the first days you have enough food (and water) but how longer it takes, you get hungry. Market: the market is not beautiful but it has the things you need. School: school is stressful and you hope you are good enough to go to America.
- When the camps are with areas you know the people in the area. You only get limited water and rationed food. In the sleep area are a lot of "houses" side by side and you hear everything. At the market there are a lot of people and only a few places. In this camp it has a dirty field for the kids to play football on or just meet friends. The school in the camps are not very good because there are too many children and only a few people who can teach. There are also not the right resources for teaching.

- I think Omar knows that other people have bad dreams, because all of these people know, how it is to flee out of their country. These bad dreams in the night are very stressful and not really funny. These families in the refugee camp get food but not too much. In the first 10 days they have a lot of food, but the last 5 days they don't have enough food and all the people are very angry. Other people can't sleep.
- The life in a refugee camp is hard. They don't have much water and food. It's also a bit fun because they can play with friends and have fun together. Like they play football or just hang out. It is also hard, because they have to clean their huts and do not have many clothes and have to wear the same clothes every day. They also have a school but it's not the same like we have. They don't have the equipment like us.
- From what I've seen about refugee camps, living there isn't the best. You have to live with other people around you and sometimes even deal with hunger. Experiencing this would probably be very hard, but still it is better than being in a country where war is. It is a blessing if you have shoes there, because everywhere everything is very muddy and dirty. Also there you get a tiny bit of food every 15 days but usually you run out of food very quickly. In the closet there is only one set of clothes most of the time. And you have to get up very early to get water because it is not available the whole day.
- Life is not easy. They don't have food every day. They must wait for food and water. In the school everyone is grumpy.
- I think it could be pretty hard having to wait for everything and not getting much food. It will also be hard not knowing what will happen next. I think also frustrating wondering how long you will have to stay there for. But for some reason I think it would be relieving because if you are escaping from war you would know you are finally safe. But again if you are escaping from war it would be scary not knowing what is happening to your country or if the people are safe.
- Omar is very thoughtful and watches over his brother, hoping to one day find his lost mother again. He has a tough life but a loving foster mom. By his words and explanations as well as his facial expressions the authors let the reader know that Omar feels scared. You get food every 15 days. And water every early morning. The food doesn't last long, so many are sick. It is difficult because you try to survive and get to another place. Hopeful because all hope for a better life. sad, because many had a hard life and lost people. Boring, because they do the same things everyday.
- I think life in a refugee camp is very hard and not as nice as our life. I think that the life in a refugee camp is poor, and the streets are dirty because there is a lot of trash on the floor. They have to get up early because they want to get water.
- I think it's very hard, because of food, houses, school, etc. The hardest thing is that they can't do the simple things which we are doing.

Task 4a (framing and positioning)

- In the top picture they wanted you to see more than the boat because they wanted to show that they are nowhere near land.
- On the second picture we are looking at Omar's story like it's first person. I guess that's so because we are looking especially what they are doing. The pictures give different vibes, the first one feels like a calm long trip, but the second one is more of a search after his mother.
- On the first picture we see much more of the place but we only see the people from far behind. I think it's because on the first picture they want to show what the boat has to cross.
- The color blue dominates, and you see white. On the second picture you see it also from the back. I think at least every color is in use. In the upper picture you look from far away but in the under picture you see it like you have the eyes of the boys. I think they choose the far away perspective to show how big the ocean is and that it is difficult to make it over the ocean. In the under picture they chose the perspective from Omar to show the different sides.
- At the under picture you feel like you are Omar/Hassan and you see their perspective from the story. At the under they wanted that you see like Omar's perspective and you feel like you're a character from the book.
- Because the authors would help you to see the view of these people on the second picture. In the first picture these people would show you not the view of the people but of the whole situation. That these people are lonely on this ocean.

Task 4c

- I like the first picture more but I feel more like I'm in the story in the second one. It is like I'm looking at them as if I was their big sister or something. I'm always right behind them, like I always got their backs. It just looks as if I would watch them grow up from the back.
- The framing and perspective of the second picture, makes me feel like I'm standing right behind them.
- I feel like the positioning in picture 2 makes me feel as if I'm part of the story. And the positioning in picture 1 makes me feel like it's a story that already happened, because of the text. In a book I would prefer the first picture, because of the text coming with it.
- The bottom picture of task a makes me feel like I'm a part of this story, because the image shows the perspective of Omar and Hassan. I can exactly see, what Omar and Hassan see.
- The under picture makes me feel more like I am in the story, because the perspective is more zoomed in and you feel like you're in the eyes of the boys.

- The picture on the bottom looks more like you're a person because you see more details and you look like from the view of a person.
- In my opinion the second picture makes me feel like I'm a part of a story and I'm experiencing everything right behind the two boys standing in front of the fence. The perspective often leads to the feeling of being part of the story. The framing also really matters because it's very important and it matters what the character is seeing.
- I think the second image makes me feel more a part of the story, because of the framing of the image. It makes me feel like I am standing behind the boys and am there for looking at the situation from their perspective.
- I think the readers can more feel about a situation in the second picture because the reader can see what the character sees. It adds more atmosphere.

Task cultural observations a)

- I think you see that they are in another culture. The people are much more bored than us because they're waiting very much. They are writing things on the floor. I think they have like a food market and that they cook so they get food.
- They wear short T-shirts and pants. Women wear long skirts and scarves. Playing, working, doing household, going to school. Ramadan. Bread and candy.
- Lots of people don't have shoes. If they did, they would wear flipflops. Also, I think all of the women have headscarves on. Some of the kids play football with a ball of plastic bags and study. They celebrate Ramadan and Eid Al-Fitr. They get maize, salt, and cooking oil. Sometimes they get flour.
- The women have scarves, and the men have normal clothes. They play football and go to school. They celebrate Eid Al-Fitr. They eat meat, vegetables, and fruit with their neighbors.
- Most people dress very simply and wear the same clothes almost every day. Little kids stay at home and play around, older kids go to school or stay at home. Adults are working or taking care of their home. The kids often go out and play with other kids. They celebrate Ramadan and usually eat and drink tea, sugar, and porridge /rice.
- The women wear hats to cover their hair. The men dress normally like other people do, but they don't wear shoes. People spend time with other people. They talk to each other or play games. They celebrate the End of Ramadan with Eid-Al Fitr, a big holiday. They eat soup because they don't get a lot of food.
- The people wear very simple clothes. They wear the same every day.
- The people dress very easily with T-shirt and shorts. The people spend time playing outside with friends. They celebrate the end of Ramadan because they are Muslims. They eat maize, cooking oil and salt.

- They wear the same clothes all the time. With the “useless” things, they make things like a football. They get rations and they save as much food as they can.
- The people are mostly in flip-flops, shorts, and a T-shirt. They spend their time playing football or telling each other stories. They pray for their parents or other people. They are waiting in three lines for oil, maize and salt.
- Males are in shorts and they wear T-shirts. Females are in some type of tissue. People are talking with each other and creating games. They celebrate Ramadan. They are getting some food like flour, salt, and oil.
- They have colorful clothes and girls have T-shirts on till their head. They go to school, wait for food, play games. They celebrate events like Ramadan and other Muslim events. They eat what the UN gives them.
- People wear the same clothes every day, if they have a celebration they buy new ones, if they have enough money. They study, clean up, make repairs around their tent, go to school or work, take care of their family and prepare for their interview. They celebrate Ramadan. They get maize, cooking oil and sometimes flour and cook something out of it.
- They dress the same close to all the time. They play football or build a small house with the things they have. They celebrate and pray together. They have a card to get food every 15 days, also after the prayed they can ask for candy from grown-ups.
- People usually only have one set of clothes that they wear every day. They play football or hang out with friends and family. They celebrate Eid Al-Fitr, the end of Ramadan. They have candy on Eid Al-Fitr.
- They dress with old clothes or random fabric. They spend their time doing chores or working, children sometimes play. Eid, a holiday is full of prayers and everyone is happy. They have to stand in long lines and they give you portions.

Task cultural observations b)

- I think they are Muslim, and I think it's important to them.
- They are Muslim.
- They are Muslim and religion is very important to them. They all got together for praying and celebrating.
- They are Muslims and celebrate Ramadan, their religion is important to them.
- They are Muslims and it seems to be very important to them.
- Muslim.
- I think Islam because they pray on their knees.
- They are Muslims because they have Ramadan.
- Islam, it's very important to them and they are very religious.
- They are Muslims and yes the religion is important to them.

- Islam, it's very important to them and they are very religious.
- Islam.
- I think the majority of the people there are Muslim.
- They are Jewish. Yes it is, it gives them hope.
- I think it is very important to them because the women wear headscarves.

Task cultural observations c)

- Because they have nothing else. That's all what they get so they have to be happy, or they may not get anything anymore.
- Because they don't always do / can do whatever they want since they are in a refugee camp.
- I think they haven't an other choice, because they can't eat other things because they haven't more/other food. The same with the clothes they can't buy others. And with the time they have they do the best in my opinion.
- Because they don't always do or can do whatever they want since they are in a refugee camp.
- Because they probably don't have much else to do and can't afford new clothes. The ones they have were probably donated. With the money and food stamps they receive they don't have much.
- I don't think they have many things to do so they can pretty much do whatever they want. But they also don't have many opportunities to do things.
- Because they have no other choice and no money.
- Because there is not that much to do at such a camp and they pray to get a "normal" life again.
- Because they don't have any way to do something else.
- Eat: because they can't differently. Dress: because it's hot. Spend their time: soccer is perfect because you only need a ball and a field.
- They can't eat something other, they need to play simple things because they have no luxury like us and they live so because they got no big shops and luxury like us and they need to live with simple things.
- They can't do anything else.
- I think they sort of have to spend their way like that and eat and dress like that because they don't have much money.
- Because they don't have many options and also have to work, cook, and look out for their family.
- I think they don't have many things they have to do or to do something with.

Task cultural observations d)

- 1. I would still want to go to school because even if it's not my favorite thing, it's good. 2. Play football in my free time, because I just love it and I just would
- I would have still wanted to go to school and be able to get at least some education.
- I would still want to go to school for my future and I would also want to play games and have fun there.
- Play football and I would do that because I do it and it's fun. I would also hang out with friends because it would help you to keep occupied and it would be fun.
- Eat when and what I want because nutrition is very important to me, and I probably would not feel well if I couldn't eat for a long time. Be with my dog, family and my friends, because I couldn't live without them. Go to school because education is important.
- Playing chess because I like playing chess and I would have unlimited time to practice playing. Doing sports because I can't think of me not doing a sport as a hobby.
- I would be learning and playing with friends.
- Hang out with friends because it's nice to talk with friends when something bad happened. I would still want to go to school because when you don't go to school you don't learn anything anymore.
- Football, because I like the way to move and when I play football I forget bad things. Meet friends because it's important because I can have a lot of fun with them.
- Play football because it's one of the best things in the world and play or listen to music because it's the other best thing in life.
- Play volleyball and spend time with family and friends.
- I would still want to play handball, because it's a thing in my life that I have done for so long and it is fun. I also would want to write my friends over the phone because they are also part of my life.
- I go to school and play with other refugee kids.
- I would want to go to school because then I have something to spend my time doing. I would also want to row even though I think I won't be able to in a refugee camp because they probably don't have a lake, let alone a boat.
- Talk with friends (if I had some), do sports and chill. Because you have relaxing and active times, it is what I need.
- Do a hobby like football and go to school, because I still want to learn new things and still have a hobby that is real fun to do.

Task emotions b)

- He is scared and sad and I think a little bit angry because he doesn't smile and the pictures show his emotions.

- At first he was nervous and scared about the interview. Then he was like excited and sure about his interview. And many years later he was like sad and disappointed in himself, because he didn't have an answer from America.
- He feels nervous, alert and bored. He was waiting a long time, not knowing if it was a waste or not but hoping to be selected.
- He starts to feel angry, annoyed and sad in chapter 13 because he didn't get accepted. I think this is because how he acts around other people, he started to push them away.
- Nervous
- Omar seemed to feel sad, bored and I think happy, because he got finally accepted to go to America. Sad because of the tears, tiny movements and his words choice. Bored he was walking around doing nothing. Happy: smile on the face.
- He feels sadness because he cries a lot and is always very down. He also feels anger because he screamed a lot and talked pretty angry because of the think words.
- Fear, anger and sadness. I think the text and the facial expression says a lot of Omar's emotions.
- He is in his bed looks sad and has little tears in his eyes. He is angry because Hassan slows Omar down so he is yelling at him. He was happy as he got the first interview for going to America.
- Insecurity, happy, responsible.
- Apprehensive because he is waiting for the interview. Sad because he is waiting for a long time. Scared.
- He was waiting all the time, he was nervous first, he was calm though. I would be nervous all the time.
- I could tell he was angry because he was yelling at other people and stomping. I could also tell that he was happy because he was smiling. He was sad and cried.
- Anger: he yells at his friends and at his brother. Sadness: he was getting a little depressed because he didn't get an answer. Happiness: because he got an interview (a chance to go to the USA).
- I think he feels happy/sad/bored/anticipation/nervousness because of the interview and the envelope they might get.
- Sadness, hope, betrayed because he expressed it in the book.
- Joy, fear, angry. In the chapter 16 he's happy but also afraid that he won't come in. in chapter 13 he's angry and scared because they never replied to him.

Task emotions c)

- They're looking hopeless, sad, tired, bored. I think they look like they don't know what happens next.

- Colors are gray, dark blue, dark green. It makes like hopeless and sad atmosphere. Their faces are also sad.
- Mostly darker colors were used and the people had sad faces and some were crying, probably because they weren't the ones to be selected.
- All of the faces look sad. Some of them are crying.
- They are sad because they can not go to America.
- The used colors aren't colorful, they're more darker colors that make the scene look more sad. Everybody looks sad and with tears and on the ground there are opened envelopes that probably say that those people didn't get accepted to go to America.
- The colors are dark. They all feel sad because of the thing that happens next. They are looking down and look sad someone covers their face with their hands.
- I think sadness and exhaustion. At the most of the faces are the hands in it to wash the tears away. The people wear dark clothes.
- They all have dark colors on and they all look sad and the little girl has tears in her eyes.
- They are no "happy" colors like yellow or red. Their faces look very sad and it seems like they've been through a lot.
- The most of them are crying so I think they are sad.
- There were gray colors. They were nervous.
- The faces of the family look very sad. Some are crying and sobbing. Their clothes are very dark. I think they feel like that because they got the thin and not the thick envelope.
- They used more of dark colors because they lost their chance for a better life. they all were very sad and they were crying.
- They look sad. I think because their application was denied. They probably have to spend most of their life in Dadaab.
- They most likely got devastating news, that's why they are sad.
- They are all feeling sad, down, scared. If they can't go to America they will have to keep on living in that camp and nobody wants that.

Task emotions d)

- I think the blue color stands like for hopefulness so I think yes, there is a connection between the colors in the background.
- Omar was just so full of emotions and couldn't forget America. The colors mostly matched his temper and emotions in the story. In both chapters he has the same emotions.
- In chapter 16 it is mostly pink in the background where in chapter 14 the colors in the background change between yellow, pink and blue.
- Yes, not all the time or the most time has a connection.

- 14 red: sad and angry, red mostly represents anger so it's used to show Omar's anger. 16 white: in my opinion it represents calmness or even sadness.
- The colors are dark that symbolizes that they are nervous and sad when the interview started and the whole chapter was always Omar sad or angry.
- Anger = red, because when a person is angry their face is red. Sadness = blue, because of the tears.
- Yeah, there are connections, like: they both have dark colors around them when they are sad and light colors for happy emotions.
- The color blue shows the sadness in both chapters, but the yellow one is in chapter 16 "darker" so it looks more sad.
- Omar was very nervous. The color red is for angry, yellow for happiness and blue for sadness.
- In chapter 14 Omar is angry and very nervous. In chapter 16 he is kind of nervous. So first he was nervous that he wouldn't go to the USA then he was nervous and calm.
- In chapter 14 Omar was happier than in chapter 16 because he had high hopes to move to America. In chapter 16 he slowly lost all his hope. I think that's why they used brighter and happier colors in chapter 14.
- In the moments he was angry we got the focus on his red t-shirt (red, the color of danger). It was all dark when he was the saddest, we only saw him to see that he is especially very sad.
- At the start Omar and Hassan felt nervous for their interviews and applications but then they had to wait for so long it turned into boredom and disappointment but I think they still had a lot of hope till the end.
- In chapter 16 there are less bright colors and seems to be less happy.
- Red, blue, purple, yellow. Almost every color because he feels angry, fear, sadness and joy in these chapters. I think though he mostly feels scared because he doesn't know or didn't know if he will go live in America.

Culture journal 2

- Because there is war and it's not safe for them. It may be that they don't have a house and food because they don't get enough money. I think it just really depends if the country is safe. If there's no safe countries in Africa then go to Europe. If there is a safe country in Africa, I would go there instead.
- 1. Resource crisis, such as shortage of food and water. 2. War reasons, most people that are in a war don't want to be part of it, the next best option is leaving. If they flee to Europe they could have a better education, but depending where you are fleeing to Europe is a very long way, so Africa would be the safest option.

- I think that people would leave their homeland because of poverty which can lead to hunger and many other unpleasant living conditions like war. Sometimes fleeing to Africa may be bad because some countries may deport you. another bad reason is that some places may also not have ideal living conditions. But otherwise if you flee somewhere in Africa if the situations get better you could get back easier.
- Because their land is in danger. War, no food, or storms, etc. because they found a better job and have to leave their country for it. I still think it's better for them to go to Europe but I guess they like it more in their continent.
- People leave their homelands because of a war or because of a political reason. I think it's better if people flee to Europe because I suppose it's safer than Africa. But if the people don't have enough money to flee to Europe and to live there, I assume it would be better for them to just flee to a different country in Africa.
- Because it is dangerous and there is war or no food left because of a natural disaster.
- People leave their country because of reason (war, natural disaster, hungry, unemployment). I think its better to flee to Europe, because in Africa like most of politicians don't even care about people, so they are poor.
- Because there is war or a catastrophe destroyed your house. Sometimes it's better to stay in the country because you understand the language and the people. But sometimes it's safer to leave the country for example when a war expands more and more.
- People leave their country because of war or hunger etc. they could probably live a better life in another country. I think it's better to flee to Europe because the countries are further developed.
- They leave their country because it's war. They leave it because they have small resources (water, food, etc.). I personally say it's better in Europe because they have a lower chance for natural catastrophes and they have enough food and water.
- One reason is when a war brakes out and the second is when the family has no food at home and all of this family is hungry.
- People leave their homelands because of wars, because many people die in wars or lose their home it's always too insecure. People leave their home also because of natural catastrophes like fire or tsunami or other things like that, because they can also lose their home. I think it's better to flee in a country in Europe because I think in Europe it's secure. It can also be secure to flee to countries in Africa. When you flee to Africa it's less expensive than to flee to Europe.
- I think that it depends on the situation. If you want to continue a similar life you have been living so far, I would stay in a different country in Africa. But if I wasn't happy with the life, that I have been living, I would start over in Europe.

- The first reason is why he has no food and not water. The second reason is why in his homeland is a war.
- People might have to leave their homelands because of war or hunger. I think it depends on the person fleeing and where they are coming from. I do think some places in Europe are safer than Africa but if a person has family somewhere in Africa or feels safer there, then go there. So it really depends on the person.
- 1 because of war. Either they don't want to be involved or they want to survive. 2 because of natural catastrophes. Maybe their house burnt down or they don't have enough food and water. I would come to Europe because it is (in my opinion) safer and cleaner. But as an African you don't speak any European language. That can be a struggle.
- Because of war, conflict, natural catastrophes, etc.
- People leave their countries because of war or poverty and hunger. I think it is better to flee to Europe because it is safer than Africa and there are less poor people which can help the refugee.
- I think they leave their homeland because of war. Or because of racism.

Culture journal 3

- In Switzerland the country is different so it's not that hot than in Kenya. Maybe it will be better because Switzerland is not that poor like Kenya so they can feed more people.
- Besides food, looks and language, probably everything would be the same. Because people who help in such camps try to help. And that is the same everywhere.
- If there was a refugee camp in Switzerland, I think there wouldn't be tents because in winter here it gets very cold, and tents wouldn't be warm. I think they would use a hut somewhere in the forest and have a bit of electricity. But like at the camp in Dadaab I think they would have a school, a hospital and maybe even a church.
- In Switzerland there would be a house, whereas in Kenya there is a tent. The two camps both have many people.
- In Switzerland there would be a bigger budget which could be invested in more and better food. The refugees need shelter with more space. The similarities are the purpose of the refugee camps which are the same in Switzerland and Kenya and also their use.
- There are also so many people. I think it looks more beautiful because Switzerland has more trees than Kenya. A difference would also be the climate because it's not so hot here. I think the huts would also be the same, but it's not so dry in Switzerland.
- In Switzerland I think it has better food and the houses are better.
- Different: more clean water, not so hot weather, less place for camps because it doesn't have big fields like Kenya. Similar: they both have only

one bed and no luxury, the people are the same and they both have medical help.

- Similar: hospital, school, huts. Different: climate, water quality, food
- I think in Switzerland are also many people but in Switzerland I think it's more beautiful than in Kenya because there are more trees.
- Difference is the climate, supplies, shelters (tents). Similar aspects are: there are many people, many shelters, some people going to flee or stay.
- The houses, huts, buildings would be small. Pretty bad climate (Kenya: very warm, Switzerland: warm in summer, cold in winter). The Swiss camp would probably be smaller, but the life conditions would be better and the buildings would be better equipped.
- I think a refugee camp in Switzerland is much smaller than the refugee camp in Kenya. The weather in Switzerland is a lot colder and there is more rain. The people who flee to Switzerland would live in containers.
- In Switzerland all refugees are going to have enough food and water. They also might have better chances at getting better education. The place also is not only richer, the place is also better in temperature and luxury (better places to sleep, etc.)
- A difference would be the climate because in Kenya it's much dryer and hotter than in Switzerland. But I think that the one in Dadaab would be bigger than the one in Switzerland. I think the living conditions would be harsher in Dadaab (climate). I'd say that in both you wouldn't have much more than a place to sleep. I think that in both you would have some medical help. I think that in both your most basic necessities are supplied (water, food, bed).
- In Switzerland refugee camps have a larger budget which leads to better food and shelter. It's also less dangerous than in Kenya, because there are no wars in Switzerland. The similarities are that both camps are served for the same purpose and there are people from all around the world.
- Similar: the people would feel all the same (kind of), it would be quite big, it is for people that have to leave their country. Different: it is less expensive in Kenya, it would be more like a normal house here, fresh tap water.

Culture journal 4

- I think how Omar explained how he felt was pretty matching to what I would say. Kids faint in school, they have seizures, they are not healthy. They hunger. If I would get food every 15 days and it wouldn't be enough I would get mad. Really mad. I wouldn't know how to express myself. I would also be grateful at the same time after all I would still get food at least. I mean there are people with no food and if you have it I would be grateful for it. Yes, the place might not be the best and yes, it might be dirty and everything but at least I got something. If I would be with my

family there then I would be happy but if my mum was gone or something like that I wouldn't feel the same anymore.

- It would be hard to adjust and it would be hard, I would feel scared, afraid, and helpless. There wouldn't be enough food and water. If I was without a parent, it would be much worse. You wouldn't know where they would be. But it would teach you the values of being alive and healthy and even getting an education. You would be grateful for what you've got and what is given to you. I would want to get an education and travel.
- I think it would be very tough to live in a refugee camp because you have to leave your home behind and maybe also some family. It would also be difficult to adjust from a life where you maybe didn't have to worry as much about food and water. I also think that maybe I would be relieved that you are safe even though you aren't home free yet. Being in the camp also must be very hard because you lost everything you had and Omar lost his mother which is probably mega sad and he had his brother and no one else. That is very sad.
- I think it's really bad to live at a refugee camp. You haven't got much food and you don't have books, phones and lots of things that are important to life. Getting food and water is very hard so everything is hard. If I would live in a refugee camp I would feel helpless and hopeless. I wouldn't like it at any way. For them it's like waiting for a wonder to happen. They don't have much space in school and they don't have good items to learn. But the sad thing is they can't really go away because they could starve or thirst to death. Also if you would get medical problems like cancer, I think your life really is over.
- I would be very sad if I had to leave my country and my home because I wouldn't be able to do the things I do now and my day would look very different. I think living in a refugee camp would be very stressful for me because there are a lot of people in a small place and I guess I wouldn't have a room for myself, so I wouldn't have privacy. Also I think the access to clean water, food, healthcare and education is limited in refugee camps, so this would also be very challenging for me. I like to take a shower every day, but I assume there isn't a shower for every person so I wouldn't be able to take my daily shower or I had to wait in line for a long time. Also I think sleeping would be difficult, because there might be someone snoring and that would disturb me.
- I would be very sad that I had to get away from my home and get to such a place where life quality is pretty bad. I would also be a bit happy that I got a place where I can live, get friends, have a hut/tent and maybe go to school. I think it would be very bad because of the radical change in my life (from how I live now to life in a refugee camp) and because I may have lost some family members. There are no positive aspects to get to such a camp.

- It would be sad. People are living in the tents, they are always hungry, they don't have enough supplies and a long way to go to school. If I would be in Omar's place I would be sad and live without a mom is hard. You can't lie on a soft bed. Everyone is poor and I'm going to feel so bad. People would be waiting in the line for water and food. People are waiting for "UN" and they don't know if they going to move other country or stay here. I guess it seems to refugees never-ending.
- I would feel sad because I lost my home. I also feel happy because I escaped from what's wrong in my country and I am away from that. In a refugee camp I would play often with friends because then you may be happier than before. It could be that you lost your parents in the war or when you fled. Then it's very sad because you have no one to help you or to bring food. Suddenly you have to do all by yourself. I would feel annoyed of the sand because I hate sand when its everywhere you sleep or eat. A refugee camp is very big. You can get lost and you hunger. In the houses is not too much space for two boys. Maybe you can't go to school or you can't speak read or write.
- It is the same every day. You always wait for things to get better but this is difficult. When you are older things are getting more difficult -> care kids, get money etc. you can build friendships. You may be always hungry and with a brother it's more stress. The main goal is to get food. I probably would feel angry because other people have way more than me and I can do nothing about it.
- In one way it would be amazing in a camp because you don't have war and you are in safety. The other way is that you are sad because you needed to leave your home, your country and probably lost your friends. I would feel really sad and angry, because I needed to flee from my home, and angry on the people who started war or made problems in the country. It would be very different because you don't can just eat food and drink water when you want because you only have limited food and water and you don't have the classic school with computers, paper and pens, the internet for your handy and electric things. In a camp you need to get new friends and need to orientate yourself in a new location. But with the time I would get more comfortable and would get happier with my life.
- I think it would be not really funny. I know it has a sleep place and you get food, but in this country that you have lived a war breaks out and it's could be that your dad and your brother must go fight. On the way from your country to the refugee camp you can lose your family and many more. I think I was happy in this camp but I would miss a lot and that would make me tired. For example I would miss my whole family, my friend, my country, my home and much more.
- For me it would be hard in a refugee camp, because we have a high standard in Switzerland. But I also think when your whole life is like Omar's life it would be easier but after all it would be not easy. So you have to clean,

you don't have pretty much food and water and to all this you have also school. But the good side of all is you also can have fun with your friends doing sports or just hanging out. There is one more problem when you get sick and your body can't heal you, you have a problem because in a refugee camp they don't have the medication to heal. So for me it would be really hard, and I would feel like normal, because it's a normal life for people that live there for their whole life. I also would feel sometimes sad, because when I would lose my mother I would feel pretty sad.

- After leaving the country I've been living in, it would be very sad but at the same time good to escape from the situation there. Since I'm not comfortable about living around many people and to deal with them every day. If I would have to wear the same things every day it would be horrible, since I am a person who loves shopping and needs a big choice what to wear. But still the most horrible part is to hunger but still going to school. I would be grateful to have the opportunity to live there instead in a country where there is war right now. I'll have to learn about the world and the life of the grown-ups. I will also have to manage my problems on my own, because my parents wouldn't have the nerves to solve them, because they have enough things to worry already. I will hope to get an opportunity to go to Europe and live a happy life there and earn and manage my own money.
- When I live in a refugee camp then I know not what I have for emotions. I was happy I have a new home anyway. I was sad my old home is away. I have food but other people have no food. Children have no parents or he has parents but she is not in the refugee camp. I feel like a captive because I can not go home, but I feel safe because I have food, a home, and water. I would be my whole life in the refugee camp. In the refugee camp I must wait and wait all day and weeks. I must wait for eat and water. As a child I go to school and as an adult I go to work. Maybe I can go to another country of another continent. I can better work in this country. Or is this a dream in the night in the refugee camp.
- Living in a refugee camp would be scary. If you're in a refugee camp it's because something bad is happening in your country. And I would feel really scared knowing that something bad is happening in my country, knowing that people might be suffering. But in some ways because of tough reasons I might feel relieved because I would finally be safe. But being in a refugee camp is sort of like the beginning though, because you have to wait for the next chapter of your life to begin. You don't really know how long you will be there for and where you will go after and that would be for me anyway really frustrating. Not knowing what will happen next. I obviously don't know completely if it would feel like that or be like that but from what Omar was saying in Chapter 6 I think it could be something like that.

- I would feel grateful and ungrateful because I would have a house, almost enough food, and probably my family or friends with me, but there would also be people with much better lives. That would frustrate me the most. I think living in such a camp would also teach many people a valuable lesson. One could learn how to survive, stay strong and have a heart. For me living in such a camp would be so different and hard. I am used to getting a warm meal everyday and having enough food and water. Being on my phone or chilling in my room while listening to music. And also calling and texting with people. Almost everything I do to keep myself busy is different than doing the things I would have to do if I were there. I would probably be miserable there. It is just a too different world. Just thinking about it gives me the chills.
- If I was in a refugee camp I would be so nervous and scared, because of new people, rules, about food. Sad, because it's hard to leave your home.
- I think it is not fair that many people have so much food so they waste it and the people in the refugee camps are hungry all the time. So when I would be in a refugee camp I would feel hunger, sad, scared, and other horrible feelings. I feel sorry for the people because they haven't done anything wrong but still are in these camps. I think we have to help these people. I can understand when presidents say there is no more space in their country, but they can still help. The refugees they lost so much. So they don't have to live in refugee camps and on the streets. And the people have to stop wasting food, so not so much people have to be hungry and have to live poor. Another point is that the presidents should stop with war and not look away and ignore the poor people.

Culture journal 5

- I think we have in common that we are both caring and that we both have siblings. I also think that we are both hardworking people, only he is more than me. I speak Spanish and I am/was probably not scared. I also think that he is one of the strongest little boys.
- We don't have much in common at all since I don't know his characteristics yet.
- Similarities: family, hobbies, school. Differences: meeting his real mother, the fact that his family (including meeting his mother) is like 2/3, that he can't really do hobbies.
- My identity wheel has a lot more facts than Omar's. I'm an older sister of a brother and Omar is an older brother of a brother. That's a similarity we share. We both are students and learn a language. He can speak Somali, but I can't. He is a refugee, and I am an adventuress.
- I live in a house; he lives in a hut. I had an easy childhood, he didn't. I had nearly unlimited water, he had to wait hours for a few liters. We both like to do sports and spend time with our brothers.

- We are from other countries. I have 2 sisters and he has one brother. We are both refugees.
- Family is for us important. We both go to school. We both want to help our brother. He has a foster mom, and I don't. for him an iPad is not important. He has no parents.
- We both like to play football and are smart (not in an arrogant meaning).
- We both like to play football, are the biggest of the family and are helpful. Omar is a survivor, hard working and sad. I'm Muslim, Turk and Swiss.
- Omar has a brother, and I also have a brother. The differences are that I don't have to flee from my country, I don't live in a refugee camp, and I always have water to drink.
- I think we both have a lot of space in the wheel for our family. We both also have school in our wheel. We both have our hobbies in the wheel. The differences are that I have gaming and phone in my wheel, and he doesn't. I also have casual things in my wheel. They are for me casual, but not for him.
- The similarities are that both Omar and I have siblings and also other family members. The difference is that Omar had to flee from his country, unlike me. I've been in Switzerland all my life. Omar also had to flee from his country and live in a refugee camp.
- I have a sister and Omar has a brother. I have real parents, Omar does not. I live in my real home, Omar does not. Omar and I go to school. Omar is a refugee, I am not. Omar and I are big siblings.
- Omar and I are both older siblings of a brother. We are both friends and students. We're not from the same countries and don't speak the same languages. I'm also not a refugee like he is.
- We are both smart, students and friends. He is a brother, and I am a sister. He loves football and I love animals. I am Swiss and he is Somalian.
- Similarities are that we are both refugees, we have a sibling and we both go to school. The differences are that he's a boy and I'm a girl. He likes to play soccer and I like to dance. He was born in Somalia, and I was born in Ukraine.
- I think Omar had other problems. I don't have to be scared. He has a different family and different house.

Culture journal 7

- I am very happy that there is no war in Switzerland and that I had such a big luck with my family. This life here in Switzerland is way easier than life in Africa. Here you don't have to be scared and haven't lost as much. You can do whatever you want to do. And it is very sad that some people cannot do something with their life because they had to flee, and other people are the sons of the Arabic prince and get their life like a gift.

- My life is really different, but we have some similarities, like we both go to school, we have a sibling, and we are both refugees.
- We both have school and have to help in the household, but I think I have way more freedom. Because I can go further away from home than Omar can, I can do more things and don't have to follow any rules. He probably has rules at the camp. I can also do more things with my friends. His life probably doesn't have much electronic devices and internet. I see something like that, like everywhere I look. We live in different places and have almost a completely different life and lifestyle. He maybe doesn't even know how fun and exciting life can be. Or if there are cars, airplanes, motorcycles and more. It could be that he doesn't know. Omar's sadly lost his parents while I still have both.
- Life in a refugee camp is basic, like it has the basic things you need to survive like food, water and a place to sleep. But it doesn't have much of it. Like in my life I have enough food to last me weeks without being hungry, but in the refugee camp they have enough food to last them days while being hungry. My life has all the basics and more, while their life just has the basics. Life in a refugee camp doesn't have as many opportunities as my life. I think it must be hard to live if you are hungry all the time.
- In the camp all the boys play football, study at night, and have fun together. I'm alone at home and not with other girls or boys. The whole camp celebrates Eid Al-Fitr. All have fun. In my town we also celebrate but not all people come to the celebration. The refugee has not much but he makes the best of what he has. We have a lot and still don't have enough. We food every day, he does not, and we throw away food even though we know that other people don't have food.
- The life that I have observed in the graphic novel seems very tough. My life compared to Omar's life is a luxury, because I have an opportunity to get a good education, always have access to food and water and I also have a proper home. I should appreciate the things I have even though it can be tough sometimes. Most of the time what is done in the graphic novel is waiting. But still no one chooses to be a refugee, it just happens because people are trying to escape from the bad situation in their country. In a refugee camp people live in hope and hoping to start a new life in another country, in the graphic novel it is America. In a refugee camp people are having the same daily routine every day, compared to mine I can choose and plan the day the way I want.
- The life I observed in the graphic novel is way other than my life. In my life I can eat when and what I want, but in the graphic novel it's like you get all days / weeks food and not much. Like this you have for 5 or 6 days and sometimes you don't have food and you can't eat anything. In the graphic novel you can't do anything in your free time you can do almost nothing, but in my life I can do almost everything because I have more space to do at home and also outside. But I and the life I observed in the graphic novel

have things that we have to do like clean at home or things like that. But another difference is that they wear all day the same clothes and they can't buy new clothes. I have so many clothes to wear and when one has a hole or something I can buy new ones. So the life in the graphic novel is way harder than my life.

- I think I have many more options than Omar. My family always has food and we have a big house. Omar's brother Hassan is very sick and in this refugee camp they don't have the same help that there is in the US for example. He can't go to a specialist. I can go to a good school and Omar is very happy when he can go to a not really good school.
- The life I observed compared to my life is very different. In the GN-life they got limited resources, no nice park or shopping locations and life is very simple. I can drink water out of the tap whenever I want or we have a fridge with a lot of food. We have cellphones, big shopping areas, nice parks and a lot of luxury. The GN-life is bad compared to a normal life, but after the time I would get into the habit of doing something and I would probably like this life a little bit. I would love this life because you nearly play football the whole time because it's the only thing you can do there and football is my hobby. I would love to play the best thing in the world the whole day. In Switzerland I can also play football the whole day but there are a lot of other things to do, so I do other things as well.
- They don't have enough food, we eat (sometimes) because we'd like to, but they eat because they are hungry. We can do what we like to do, but they are restricted (by not everything) and have to do things again and again (get food, etc.). They always wait for things to get better but maybe it never happens. They didn't choose to be a refugee and we didn't choose to live here. For us school is the most normal thing, but for them it is special.
- Omar can't go to school because of his brother. For me it's normal to go to school every week, for him it is not. I can live with my parents and they worry about me. Omar has no parents and a little tent. With my phone I can reach my parents every time. Omar can't do this. I have a big selection of food in shops, Omar has only three ingredients.
- My life is more like smart. I don't know like it depends on what graphic novel it would be. It is going to be like a part of my life, and it is going to be like an epic story. I have no idea though.
- Already before this story I knew that life in a refugee camp is very hard and incomparable to the life of an average Swiss. Omar had to fight for food and water, I just have to open the fridge and prepare something. But it seems even harder when we see the life of an individual like Omar.
- The life of the people in the refugee camps is very basic. Unlike them I live a very luxurious life. I have enough food to last for weeks and even months without being hungry once. The people in refugee camps just have a small amount of food. It's very rare if they have two days without being hungry.

They wear the same clothes every day for months and maybe years. I on the other hand have a lot more clothes, sometimes not all of them fit in my closet. Sometimes I go shopping just for fun and buy more clothes, even though I don't need them urgently. This would never be possible in a refugee camp, because the people there don't have enough money and they probably save their money for something more important than that many clothes.

- The life of refugees is not good, they don't have enough food and they don't have things to play with. If they want to play soccer they have to make a ball out of trash bags. Also Omar and Hassan don't really have a family because they lost the mother and the father died. My life is much better. I have enough food and can do close to everything I want. I have enough clothes and I don't have to fear death when I get sick or I'm injured. All in all, we should feel good about our easy lives and don't want more stuff than we need.
- In the novel everything is depicted to be harder than we have it. I mean like getting water and having proper meals. In the book it was also mentioned that they live in little huts where there are uncomfortable beds. They also lack some basic necessities that we take for granted like public transport or a good school. In the book we saw three kids at one desk, which we wouldn't see here in Switzerland ever. There were also no real footballs.
- I personally don't have much in common with the graphic novel, but I find it impressive that they found such meaning behind seemingly meaningless objects.
- I think the kids in the refugee camp have it very different to us. Their life is way harder and what we read is sometimes their day to day life. they also have different religions (I don't have one). They had to go through a lot to just get to a refugee camp and now they live there with little to nothing. Nobody actually knows what the people go through every day if there weren't stories about Omar and Hassan. My life is totally different than theirs and definitely can try to imagine how it is, but I don't actually know unless I am in a refugee camp.